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**PROCESS ENGINEERING ASPECTS
OF DIESEL ENGINE OFF GASES
TREATMENT**

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Process engineering aspects of diesel engine off gases treatment

The purpose of this study was to investigate the currently available methods of maritime diesel engine off gases removing systems. The major cargo transportation mode is maritime transport, which is also responsible for approximately 90% of world trade by volume. Furthermore, travelling by sea has increased considerably in recent years – from 2003 to 2016 this touristic sector has expanded from 12.0 to 22.0 million travellers. Accordingly, worldwide emission from shipping has grown significantly, which contributes directly to the global anthropogenic emissions and it poses a serious threat to the ecosystem and public health.

Exhausts from marine engines may contain nitrogen, oxygen, carbon dioxide (CO₂) and water vapour as well as nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulphur oxides (SO_x), carbon monoxide (CO), various hydrocarbons (HC) and complex particulate matter (PM). The maritime transport usually uses heavy fuel oil (HFO) with a high content of sulphur, which naturally leads to the three main pollutants derived from shipping: nitrogen oxides, sulphur oxides and particulate matters. Around 15% of global NO_x and 5-8% of SO_x emissions are attributable to ocean-going ships. Sulphur dioxide (SO₂) emission as a smog component is a precursor to acid rains and it can have a negative influence on plant life as well as on wider ecosystems. The two primary nitrogen oxides present in pollution streams are nitric oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂). The molecular nitrogen in the combustion air or in the fuel is oxidized, forming NO_x. Nitrogen dioxide is a brown gas with a ripe smell whereas NO is colourless and essentially odourless as well as insoluble and non-reactive. Both of them can be contributors to acid rain or precursors to the formation of ground-level ozone (smog component), which causes respiratory problems and damage to vegetation.

To address the adverse impacts of sulphur and nitrogen oxides from shipping emission, the maritime sector is required to find highly efficient and low-cost methods of gaseous pollutants removal. According to the International Maritime Organization regulations (MARPOL Annex VI), there are two sets of emission and fuel quality requirements: global (progressive reduction in global emissions of SO_x, NO_x and particulate matter) and more restrictive requirements dedicated to ships in deliberately established zones – emission control areas (ECA). Inside the ECA it is expected to use 0.10% sulphur fuel and to achieve above 90% of NO_x removal.

Outgoing methods are applied to remove NO_x or SO₂ separately. These technologies are divided into NO_x-reducing devices and SO_x scrubbers and this work are focused on process engineering aspects of such systems, including designing of apparatus, main dimensions, advantages/disadvantages as well as processes economy and cost analysis.

To accomplished major reductions in SO_x and NO_x emissions, a new onboard installation of exhaust emission control are required and one of them may be an electron beam flue gas treatment (EBFGT) process, which is one of the most effective methods of removing SO₂ and NO_x from industrial flue gases.

In this study, the exhaust gas was first irradiated with the electron beam (EB) technology to reduce the NO, in the dose range of 10-12 kGy with a temperature of the exhaust gas not exceeding 90°C and then followed by a wet scrubber method with appropriately prepared process water, with an addition of the strong oxidant NaClO₂. The NO_x removal was above 90% and it is expected to use this method for simultaneous removal of NO_x and SO₂ in the future.

Aspekty inżynierii procesowej w oczyszczaniu spalin z silników Diesla

Celem niniejszej pracy było zbadanie metod oczyszczania spalin z silników Diesla aktualnie wykorzystywanych w transporcie morskim.

Transport morski jest odpowiedzialny za ok. 90% (objętościowo) światowego handlu. Co więcej, w ostatnich latach wzrosło zainteresowanie podróżowaniem drogą morską – w latach 2003-2016 liczba podróży zwiększyła się z 12,0 do aż 22,0 milionów. W związku z tym

odpowiednio wzrosła też ogólnoswiatowa emisja spalin ze statków, co jest poważnym zagrożeniem dla ekosystemów i zdrowia publicznego.

Spaliny silnikowe mogą zawierać azot, tlen, dwutlenek węgla i parę wodną, a także tlenki azotu, siarki, monotlenek węgla, różne węglowodory i pył. Ponieważ w transporcie morskim korzysta się głównie z tzw. paliwa HFO (ang. heavy fuel oil), o wysokiej zawartości siarki, najczęściej uwagi poświęca się trzem głównym zanieczyszczeniom: NO_x , SO_x i pyłom. Około 15% światowej emisji NO_x i 5-8% emisji SO_x jest spowodowane transportem morskim. SO_2 jako składnik smogu przyczynia się do powstawania kwaśnych deszczy i może mieć negatywny wpływ na roślinność, jak i na szersze ekosystemy. Dwa główne tlenki azotu obecne w strumieniu zanieczyszczeń są to NO i NO_2 . Dwutlenek azotu jest brązowym gazem o ostrym zapachu, podczas gdy tlenek azotu jest bezbarwny, bezzapachowy, a także trudno rozpuszczalny i niereaktywny. Obydwa tlenki mogą powodować kwaśne deszcze i być przyczyną tworzenia się ozonu troposferycznego, co prowadzi bezpośrednio do problemów z układem oddechowym oraz jest szkodliwe dla roślinności.

Celem rozwiązania problemu niekorzystnego wpływu emitowanych ze statków tlenków siarki i azotu pożądane jest wyposażenie ich w wysoko wydajne i stosunkowo niedrogie systemy usuwania spalin. Według regulacji Międzynarodowej Organizacji Morskiej – IMO (MARPOL Annex VI) są dwa rodzaje limitów emisji szkodliwych komponentów i zużywanego paliwa: globalne (progresywna redukcja ogólnoswiatowej emisji SO_x , NO_x i pyłu) oraz bardziej restrykcyjne dla statków poruszających się w wyznaczonych strefach kontroli, tzw. ECA (ang. emission control areas). Wewnątrz ECA oczekuje się użytkowania paliwa zawierającego maksymalnie 0,10% siarki oraz osiągnięcia ponad 90% skuteczności usuwania NO_x z gazów odlotowych z silników Diesla.

Dotychczasowe metody usuwania NO_x i SO_x przeznaczone są do usuwania tych tlenków oddzielnie. Technologie te można podzielić na systemy redukcji tlenków azotu oraz skrubery neutralizujące tlenki siarki. Niniejsza praca skupia się na analizie aspektów inżynierii procesowej w tych instalacjach, włączając w to projektowanie urządzeń, najważniejsze wymiary, wady/zalety, a także na analizie kosztów.

Aby osiągnąć znaczącą redukcję omawianych tlenków potrzebne są nowe technologie, możliwe do wykorzystania bezpośrednio na pokładzie. Może być nią proces oczyszczania z wykorzystaniem akceleratora, który jest jednym z najbardziej efektywnych sposobów usuwania NO_x i SO_x z przemysłowych gazów odlotowych. W tej pracy, celem redukcji monotlenku azotu NO , spaliny z silnika Diesla zostały najpierw napromieniowane wiązką elektronów o dawce 10-12 kGy (temperatura procesowa nie przekroczyła 90°C), a następnie skierowane do mokrego skrubera z odpowiednią wodą procesową z dodatkiem silnego utleniacza NaClO_2 . Wydajność usuwania NO_x wyniosła 90% i oczekuje się, iż w przyszłości możliwe będzie użycie tej metody do jednoczesnego usuwania NO_x i SO_2 .

CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	7
2. EMISSION LIMITS FOR MARINE VESSELS	8
2.1. SO _x emission limits	8
2.2. NO _x emission limits	10
3. MARINE DIESEL ENGINES	12
3.1. Four-stroke marine diesel engines	13
3.2. Two-stroke marine diesel engines	15
4. CURRENTLY AVAILABLE SO_x/NO_x EMISSION CONTROL SYSTEMS	23
4.1. SO _x pollution control	23
4.2. NO _x pollution control	44
4.3. Cost analysis	57
4.4. Simultaneous removal of NO _x and SO _x	61
5. ELECTRON BEAM	62
5.1. Introduction	62
5.2. Process key parameters	63
5.3. Accelerators for onboard applications	67
5.4. Conclusions and recommendations	70
6. LITERATURE	71

1. INTRODUCTION

The major cargo transportation mode is maritime transport, which is also responsible for approximately 90% of world trade by volume. Furthermore, travelling by sea has increased considerably in recent years – from 2003 to 2016 this touristic sector has expanded from 12.0 to 22.0 million travellers [1]. Shipping is also the most cost-effective and efficient method of international transportation for most goods. It provides a reliable means of transporting goods globally, facilitating commerce and helping to create prosperity among nations and peoples. Accordingly, worldwide emission from shipping has grown significantly, which contributes directly to the global anthropogenic emissions and it poses a serious threat to the ecosystem and public health [2].

Exhausts from marine engines may contain nitrogen, oxygen, carbon dioxide (CO₂) and water vapour as well as nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulphur oxides (SO_x), carbon monoxide (CO), various hydrocarbons (HC) and complex particulate matter (PM). The maritime transport usually uses heavy fuel oil (HFO) with a high content of sulphur, which naturally leads to the three main pollutants derived from shipping: nitrogen oxides, sulphur oxides and particulate matters [3]. Around 15% of global NO_x and 5-8% of SO_x emissions are attributable to ocean-going ships [4].

Presence of sulphur oxides in exhausts is a direct result of the fuels' composition, which was applied. During the combustion, the sulphur is oxidized, generating sulphur dioxide (SO₂) with a minor proportion of sulphur trioxide (SO₃). SO₂ emission as a smog component is a precursor to acid rains and it can have a negative influence on plant life as well as on wider ecosystems. It is also possible to observe damaging of minerals used in the construction of buildings and other architecture. In the absence of wetness (rain, snow) these gases may contain particulate matter, causing harm to human health and the environment (for instance respiratory problem, damaging vegetation) [3]. The two primary nitrogen oxides present in pollution streams are nitric oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂). The molecular nitrogen in the combustion air or in the fuel is oxidized, forming NO_x. Nitrogen dioxide is a brown gas with a ripe smell whereas NO is colourless and essentially odourless. Both of them can be contributors to acid rain or precursors to the formation of ground-level ozone (smog component), which causes respiratory problems and damage to vegetation [3-5].

The three modes of operation can be distinguished during the ship journey: at berth, manoeuvring and at sea. The emissions from manoeuvring comprise the lowest amount of pollutants whereas the majority of hazardous gases are emitted while the ship is at sea [6]. Emissions are also specific to a ship, as individual ships have varying machinery and equipment. For meeting specific requirements related to different areas (open sea, on/offshore, inland water) as well as to ships' parameters, in 1948, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) was established at the conference in Geneva. Nowadays, IMO is the global standard-setting authority for the safety of international shipping with a universally implemented and universally adopted regulatory framework for the shipping industry (including manning, construction, ship design, equipment, operation and disposal, etc.) [7].

On 2 November 1973, IMO adopted the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL), which is the main international convention covering prevention of pollution of the marine environment by ships from operational or accidental causes [7]. MARPOL is divided into annexes in relation to different categories of pollutants, each of which deals with the regulation of a particular group of ship emissions [8] (Table 1.1).

MARPOL Annex VI entered into force on 19 May 2005. It includes limits for the main air pollutants contained in ships exhaust gas and it prohibits the deliberate emissions of ozone-depleting substances. MARPOL Annex VI also regulates the emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOC) from tankers and shipboard combustion. Two sets of emission and fuel quality requirements are defined by Annex VI [9]:

- global requirements – a progressive reduction in global emissions of SO_x, NO_x and particulate matter,

- more restrictive requirements dedicated to ships in deliberately established zones – emission control areas (ECA).

Table 1.1. List of the MARPOL 73/78 Annexes [8]

Annex	Title	Entry into force
Annex I	Prevention of pollution by oil & oily water	2 October 1983
Annex II	Control of pollution by noxious liquid substances in bulk	2 October 1983
Annex III	Prevention of pollution by harmful substances carried by sea in packaged form	1 July 1992
Annex IV	Pollution by sewage from ships	27 September 2003
Annex V	Pollution by garbage from ships	31 December 1988
Annex VI	Prevention of air pollution from ships	19 May 2005

Existing ECA can be designated for SO_x and PM, or NO_x, as well as all three types of emissions from ships and it consists of [9]:

- Baltic Sea (SO_x: adopted 1997/entered into force 2005; NO_x: 2016/2021);
- North Sea (SO_x: 2005/2006; NO_x: 2016/2021);
- North American ECA, including most of US and Canadian coast (NO_x and SO_x: 2010/2012);
- US Caribbean ECA, including Puerto Rico and the US Virgin Islands (NO_x and SO_x: 2011/2014).

Due to current and upcoming regulations to address the adverse impacts of sulphur and nitrogen oxides from shipping emission, the maritime sector is required to find highly efficient and low-cost methods of gaseous pollutants removal. Outgoing methods are applied to remove NO_x or SO₂ separately. These technologies are divided into NO_x-reducing devices and SO_x scrubbers. There are only several studies concentrating on the simultaneous removal of NO_x and SO₂ in one process (using electrolysis or electromagnetic techniques) [3, 10]. To accomplished major reductions in SO_x and NO_x emissions, the new onboard installations of exhaust emission control are required and one of them may be an electron beam flue gas treatment (EBFGT) process, which is one of the most effective methods of removing SO₂ and NO_x from industrial flue gases.

2. EMISSION LIMITS FOR MARINE VESSELS

2.1. SO_x emission limits

SO_x limits are designated under Regulation 4 and 14 of MARPOL Annex VI (SO_x and particulate matter emission control). Limitations of sulphur oxide's concentration in exhausts from maritime vessels are currently met in two different ways [3]:

- primary – using fuel oil with a low sulphur content (avoiding of pollutants forming),
- secondary – using SO_x scrubber system (exhaust gas treatment system).

Limits of sulphur content are strictly related to areas on which ship moves. The sulphur limits and implementation dates are listed in Table 2.1. and illustrated in Fig. 2.1.

Most vessels which operate both outside and inside the ECA will, therefore, operate on different fuel oils. It is expected to have fully changed over to using the ECA compliant fuel oil before entering into the ECA. Likewise, a change from the ECA compliant fuel oil to the oil used outside cannot be started before leaving the ECA. The first crucial issue while meeting these limits is to have a knowledge about the actual sulphur content in the bunkered fuel oils.

Table 2.1. MARPOL Annex VI fuel sulphur limits inside/outside the ECA [9]

Outside the ECA established to limit SO _x and PM emissions	Inside the ECA established to limit SO _x and PM emissions
4.50% m/m prior to 1 January 2012	1.50% m/m prior to 1 July 2010
3.50% m/m on and after 1 January 2012	1.00% m/m on and after 1 July 2010
0.50% m/m on and after 1 January 2020	0.10% m/m on and after 1 January 2015

This value is to be stated in the special documents (bunker delivery note) by the fuel oil supplier. Subsequently, it is a crew's responsibility to possess the suitable fuel, service tanks as well as to avoid loading into differently part filled storage. Accordingly, accidental mixing of one fuel with other, higher sulphur content oil is unacceptable.

Fig. 2.1. Illustration of progressive decrease of sulphur content in fuel under MARPOL Annex VI, Regulation 14

MARPOL Annex VI determines the sulphur content in the fuel being combusted. As an equivalent for using controlled fuels, the SO_x scrubbers were applied (MARPOL Annex VI, Regulation 4). In 2009, a Guidelines for Exhaust Gas Cleaning System MEPC 184 (59), which specify the regulations for the certification, test and in-service verification of SO_x scrubbing systems were created. To meet restrict regulations, each scrubber should necessarily be approved by the ship's flag administration or by a classification society acting as a recognized organization on the flag administration's behalf. According to the Guidelines, there are two schemes, acceptable as the alternative methods of compliance with MARPOL Annex VI, Regulation 14 [3]:

- Scheme A – there is a need for initial certification of SO_x reduction ability, followed by continuous monitoring of operating parameters and a daily spot check of emissions performance.
- Scheme B – initial certification is not required, the continuous emission monitoring using an approved system and a daily spot check of operating parameters are being used.

Using a scrubbing system always requires a SO_x Emissions Compliance Plan (SECP), which introduces how the vessel will comply with MARPOL Annex VI, Regulation 14. SECP must be prepared by ship operator and it also has to be approved by the administration. Table 2.2 shows the documents, which should be provided by the equipment manufacturer [3].

The majority of SO₂ in an exhaust system, as well as CO₂, is attributable to the fuel, combustion and operation conditions and engine design. For this reason, the ratio of SO₂/CO₂ is using to measure of SO₂ emission in proportion to the sulphur content of the fuel consumed. Therefore, in reference to scrubber system, it is possible to meet the limits included in Regulation 14 of MARPOL Annex VI on the basis of the SO₂/CO₂ ratio values listed in

Table 2.2. Scrubber document requirements [3]

Document	Scheme A	Scheme B
SO _x Emissions Compliance Plan (SECP)	X	X
SO _x Emissions Compliance Certificate (SECC)	X	
EGC system – Technical Manual for Scheme A (ETM-A)	X	
EGC system – Technical Manual for Scheme B (ETM-B)		X
Onboard Monitoring Manual (OMM)	X	X
EGC Record Book or Electronic Logging System	X	X

Table 2.3 (only applicable to the combustion of residual fuel oils and the petroleum-based distillate) [3].

Table 2.3. The fuel oil sulphur limits recorded in MARPOL Annex VI, Regulations 14 and corresponding emissions values [3]

Fuel oil sulphur content [% m/m]	Ratio emission SO ₂ [ppm]/CO ₂ [% v/v]
4.50	195.0
3.50	151.7
1.50	65.0
1.00	43.3
0.50	21.7
0.10	4.3

Under each scheme, it is required to show that the SO₂/CO₂ ratio of the scrubbed exhaust is less than or equal to the required. In relation to Scheme A the value of gas flow rate and the SO₂/CO₂ ratio are specified by the manufacturer and they must comply with ship's operating pattern and with the SO₂/CO₂ emissions being at least the equivalent of the applicable fuel sulphur limit under Regulation 14. (Generally the certified value for most scrubbers is expected to be the equivalent of using 0.10% sulphur fuel.)

Under Scheme B, a continuous emissions monitoring, showing that the SO₂/CO₂ ratio of the scrubbed exhaust is less than or equal to the recommended at any load point (including during transient operation), is compulsory.

2.2. NO_x emission limits

NO_x limits are designated under Regulation 13 of MARPOL Annex VI (NO_x emission control). Regulations are divided into three parts and they directly depend upon the date of ships construction and engine's rated speed (n). The first and the second parts of requirements are related to engines installed on ships constructed on or after 1 January 2000 (Tier I) and 1 January 2011 (Tier II). Tier III limits are in force only in NO_x emission control areas, while the Tier I and Tier II standards are global. In accordance with Regulation 13, it will not be allowed for certain small ships to install Tier III engines. The nitrogen oxides emission regulation, which is posted in MARPOL Annex VI, allows installing the marine diesel engine of over 130 kW output power, other than those used solely for emergency purposes irrespective of the

Table 2.4. MARPOL Annex VI NO_x emission limits, determined from the engine's rated speed [9]

Tier	Ship construction date on or after	Total weighted cycle emission limit [g/kWh] n = engine's rated speed [rpm]		
		n < 130	n = 130-1999	n ≥ 2000
I	1 January 2000	17.0	$45 \cdot n^{(-0.2)}$, e.g. 720 rpm – 12.1	9.8
II	1 January 2011	14.4	$44 \cdot n^{(-0.23)}$, e.g. 720 rpm – 9.7	7.7
III	1 January 2016	3.4	$9 \cdot n^{(-0.2)}$, e.g. 720 rpm – 2.4	2.0

tonnage of the ship onto which such engines are installed [3]. Permissible NO_x emission limit for vessels, specified by the International Maritime Organization in the MARPOL Convention as Tier III standard, initially assumed its validity from 1 January 2016. However, the introduction of these requirements from 1 January 2016 has become dependent on the availability of technology applying to reduce NO_x emissions to such a low level. IMO analyses have shown that the introduction of such stringent standards in the assumed period is impossible and the date of entry of the Tier III standard has been shifted, probably on 1 January 2021. Until then, NO_x emission reductions should be in accordance with Tier II [11].

The NO_x limits and implementation dates are listed in Table 2.4 and illustrated in Fig. 2.2.

Fig. 2.2. Illustration of progressive decrease of NO_x emission limits under MARPOL Annex VI, Regulation 13

Tier II regulations are expected to apply a combustion process optimization by the detailed examination of fuel injection timing, pressure, and rate (rate shaping), fuel nozzle flow area, exhaust valve timing, and cylinder compression volume. Tier III limits are expected to be met by dedicated NO_x emission control technologies, such as exhaust gas recirculation (EGR) or selective catalytic reduction (SCR).

They are three methods used to confirm that the level of nitrogen oxides emission remains within the applicable limits [3]:

- Parameter check method – checking compliance of all operational parameters. Keeping the limits specified in the engine's technical file guarantees that the appropriate NO_x level is maintained.

- Direct measurement and monitoring method while the engine is in service (engine + SCR together), referred to as Scheme A – completing data, using an approved emission monitoring system and determining specific g/kWh NO_x emission and exhaust flow rate. To be considered as current, data have to comply within 30 days of the survey.
- Separate tests of engine and SCR referred to as Scheme B – testing of NO_x emission from the engine in accordance with the appropriate test cycle and predefining of NO_x reduction performance of the SCR by modelling tools using data from either a full size or scaled down version. The g/kWh NO_x emission value is calculated in relation to these two dimensions and thereafter it is implemented into engine's technical file. Finally, the result of the simulation is confirming on board.

3. MARINE DIESEL ENGINES

Diesel engines, rather than gasoline engines, are distinguished by lower operating cost, longer durability, higher thermal energy as well as lower hydrocarbon and carbon monoxide emissions. Thus, there has been a continuous increase in the number of diesel engines operating in both stationary and mobile applications. Notwithstanding, this type of energy source emits the higher amount of PM and NO_x than gasoline engines.

Due to lack of homogeneity in the fuel and rapid variations in the temperature inside the diesel engine, it is not possible to reach the ideal state of thermodynamic equilibrium [12]. Hence, the incomplete combustion of HC results in the formations of various types of organic and inorganic compounds, distributed among the gaseous, semi-volatile and particulate phases [13]. Products of this phenomenon are presented in Table 3.1 [14].

Table 3.1. Typical diesel exhaust composition [14]

	Component	Concentration
Components naturally occurring in air	N ₂	70-75 vol%
	O ₂	5-15 vol%
	CO ₂	2-12 vol%
	H ₂ O	2-10 vol%
Regulated harmful components	CO	100-1000 ppm
	HC	50-500 ppm
	NO _x	30-600 ppm
	SO _x	proportional to fuel S content
	PM	20-200 mg/m ³
Unregulated harmful components	ammonia	2.0 mg/mile
	cyanides	1.0 mg/mile
	benzene	6.0 mg/mile
	toluene	2.0 mg/mile
	polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH)	0.2 mg/mile
	aldehydes	0.0 mg/mile

The world's leading designer and manufacturer of low and medium speed engines, using as a marine vessels' propulsion are MAN Diesel & Turbo Group and its licensees. They develop two-stroke and four-stroke engines, auxiliary engines, turbochargers and propulsion packages, which cover approximately 50% of the power needed for all world trade.

3.1. Four-stroke marine diesel engines

In the maritime environment, four-stroke engine is commonly used in on-road and marine transportation and it requires four strokes of the piston to complete a power cycle during two crankshaft revolution [15]. A stroke refers to the full travel of the piston along the cylinder, in either direction (Fig. 3.1).

Fig. 3.1. The four-stroke cycle: A – intake, B – compression, C – power, D – exhaust; 1, 2 – crankshaft revolutions

The maximum amount of power generated by an engine is determined by the maximum amount of air ingested. The amount of power generated by a piston engine is related to its size (cylinder volume), whether it is a two-stroke engine or four-stroke design, volumetric efficiency, losses, air-to-fuel ratio, the calorific value of the fuel, the oxygen content of the air and speed (rpm). The speed is ultimately limited by material strength and lubrication. Valves, pistons and connecting rods suffer severe acceleration forces. At high engine speed, physical breakage and piston ring flutter can occur, resulting in power loss or even engine destruction. Piston ring flutter occurs when the rings oscillate vertically within the piston grooves in which they are located. Ring flutter compromises the seal between the ring and the cylinder wall, which causes a loss of cylinder pressure and power. If an engine spins too quickly, valve springs cannot act quickly enough to close the valves [15]. This is commonly referred to as 'valve float', and it can result in the piston to valve contact, severely damaging the engine. At high speeds, the lubrication of piston cylinder wall interface tends to break down. This limits the piston speed for industrial engines to about 10 m/s. The output power of an engine is dependent on the ability of intake (air-fuel mixture) and exhaust matter to move quickly through valve ports, typically located in the cylinder head. An internal combustion engine on an average is capable of converting just 30-40% of the supplied energy into mechanical work. A large part of the waste energy is in the form of heat that is released to the environment through coolant, fins, etc. It has been found that even if 6% of the entirely wasted heat is recovered it can increase the engine efficiency greatly [16]. Many methods have been devised in order to extract waste heat out of an engine exhaust and use it further to extract some useful work, decreasing the exhaust pollutants at the same time. Use of Rankine cycle, turbocharging and thermo-electric generation has been found very useful as a waste heat recovery system.

Depending on the operational location and type of the ship, different four-stroke engines with desired parameters are used. Main applications of four-stroke diesel engines are presented below.

Offshore: Offshore vessels require highly reliable and efficient propulsion systems that adapt easily to low-load operation. Station keeping, also known as dynamic positioning, is another key factor when operating in heavy seas around oil platforms and installations. Offshore vessels typically operate in environmentally sensitive areas (ECA), therefore emission requirements, such as NO_x and particulate matter, are of the utmost importance. Emission limits can be met with the range of dual fuel engines or by installing one of the post-treatment systems such as selective catalytic reduction to minimize NO_x and scrubbers to reduce SO_x. While operating offshore, the highly efficient and reliable four-stroke engines are required (to power the broad variety of offshore vessels, anchor handlers, platform supply vessels, construction vessels, drill ships, etc.).

Dredger: In relation to the growth in the global sea transport and the size of marine vessels, greater demands have been placed on harbours and commercial waterways around the world. Part of the solution lies in excavating channel beds and modern dredgers are capable of excavating gigantic volumes of sediment daily. Modern dredgers require highly reliable, efficient, proven, medium-speed, four-stroke engines that comply with all modern emission regulations when sailing in environmentally sensitive areas (ECA). It is expected to be met by reduced rpm experienced during dredger pump operation. For engines running on heavy fuel oils, it is required to install the exhaust gas cleaning systems such as SCR to minimize NO_x and to meet IMO Tier III regulations. Modern auxiliary engines usually run on the same high-viscosity fuel grades as the main engines to maximize economy.

Fishing: As with so many other marine segments, population growth is one of the primary market drivers in the fishing industry, in this case revolving around the need for ever-more food resources. Fishing restrictions are another key influence as regulation forces on the construction of modern, cost-optimized vessels that can operate profitably. Modern fishing vessels require cost-efficient propulsion systems (with low first-costs) as well as tough and robust technical solutions for operation in what are some of the harshest and most demanding conditions on the planet. Fishing vessels typically operate in environmentally sensitive areas, therefore emission requirements, such as NO_x, SO_x and particulate matter, are important. It is expected to use the proven, efficient medium-speed engines that are eminently suitable for the fishing segment as well as to have the exhaust gas cleaning systems such as SCR for IMO Tier III-compliance (NO_x) and scrubbers for SO_x reduction to comply with IMO Tier III emission regulations and their sulphur limits. Modern auxiliary engines run on the same high-viscosity fuel grades as main engines to maximize economy.

Navy and government: The navy and coast guard segment has grown in recent years in the face of national security concerns where nations are anxious to protect their maritime boundaries. At the same time, the growth of asymmetric threats, such as piracy, has increased the desire to provide security for world seaborne trade. Requirements within this segment include highly reliable, efficient and proven propulsion systems with excellent load acceptance. While not a strict requirement, there is still a demand for limiting emissions as much as possible. Navies often make special demands on their propulsion systems, compared to civilian vessels, such as shock-proofing, noise cancellation and antimagnetic propulsion systems. Modern auxiliary engines run on the same high-viscosity fuel grades as the main engines to maximize economy.

Ferry: Driven by the global growth in population and an increase in regional trade, the mobility of people – both domestically and internationally – has increased rapidly in recent decades. Modern ferries place high demands for reliability and comfort on their main engines, while silent power generation onboard is also a crucial consideration when thinking gen-sets. As this vessel type frequently sails in coastal waters, environmental sensitivity is a key issue and minimizing NO_x, SO_x and particulate matter levels to meet stringent emission limits is a key requirement. At the same time, ferry operators seek to keep operating costs on a low level to ensure their ability to compete, also against other means of transportation. Ferry's four-stroke engines are also available as dual-fuel engines capable of running on gas, as well as on fuel oils,

to ensure compliance with existing and upcoming regulations on permissible NO_x and sulphur emissions. For engines running on HFO, it is required to install the exhaust gas cleaning systems such as SCR to minimize NO_x and scrubbers to reduce SO_x. Modern auxiliary engines run on the same high-viscosity fuel grades as the main engines to maximize economy.

LNG: Global energy demands continue to rise year after year as existing oil reservoirs become depleted and the search for replacements spreads to deeper parts of the ocean, requiring massive investment costs. A general change in energy politics has nuclear and coal power losing popularity while gas from the USA and the Middle East is emerging as a viable alternative. Political instability has also encouraged countries to develop an energy policy that makes them more independent from pipeline supplies. In this scenario, the shipping of natural gas by LNG carrier is an obvious solution. Modern LNG tankers require highly reliable propulsion systems with excellent service support as engine availability is critical. Sailing globally through environmentally sensitive waters demands low engine emissions while the operational safety of the propulsion system is paramount. Offered propulsion systems should, therefore, be efficient and proven and they also should be able to comply with all modern emission legislation when sailing in environmentally sensitive areas and which meet the strict safety requirements that LNG carriers operate under. Some of MAN's Diesel & Turbo engines are dual-fuel and they can both operate on boil-off gas derived from a carrier's LNG payload and diesel-electric engine solutions. Modern auxiliary engines run on the same high-viscosity fuel grades as the main engines to maximize economy.

Cruise: As global wealth has grown in recent decades and the concept of enjoying a foreign holiday has become standard for many people, so accordingly the cruise trade has grown. Once the preserve of the very rich, cruises are now affordable to many and this segment has experienced significant growth. Today's cruise ships must accommodate high demands for reliable, comfortable and silent power generation onboard. As cruise vessels typically sail in environmentally sensitive areas, the engines employed in this segment must meet stringent emission regulations in terms of NO_x, SO_x and particulate matter. While ensuring minimal impact on the environment operators also seek to keep operating costs at economic levels in order to offer affordable holiday experiences to their customers. Four-stroke engines, used while cruise, are available as dual-fuel engines capable of running on gas, as well as on fuel oils, to ensure compliance with existing and upcoming regulations on permissible NO_x and sulphur emissions. For engines running on fuel oils, it is expected to use the exhaust gas cleaning systems such as SCR to minimize NO_x and scrubbers to reduce SO_x. Modern auxiliary engines run on the same high-viscosity fuel grades as the main engines to maximize economy.

Tug: The global growth in marine transport and the accompanying increase in the volume and complexity of harbour operations have expanded the tug sector in recent years. Simultaneously, the general increase in vessel size, such as that experienced within the container and tanker sectors, has prompted the development of larger, more powerful tugs. Modern tugs require cost-efficient propulsion systems (with low first-costs), while the nature of harbour operations demands that engines possess great adaptability to low-load operation. Harbours are also environmentally sensitive areas and, accordingly, emission requirements are strict in terms of NO_x and particulate matter. In this case, it is required to use medium-speed engines that are eminently suitable for the tug segment. The operation profile of a tug is pretty much as a 'sleeping bear' – many hours of standby just waiting and then full power on all engines. It requires a lot of the engine to be able to handle those load challenges a tug is requiring. All tugs' engines are therefore equipped with jet-assist which boosts the turbocharger speed if sudden load peaks occur resulting in rapid and smoke-free load increase.

3.2. Two-stroke marine diesel engines

In a two-stroke engine, the end of the combustion stroke and the beginning of the compression stroke happen simultaneously, with the intake and exhaust (or scavenging) functions occurring at the same time. In contrast to a four-stroke engine, it completes a power cycle with

Fig. 3.2. Flow process and typical exhaust gas composition for two-stroke diesel engine [17]

two strokes (up and down movements) of the piston during only one crankshaft revolution. Two-stroke engines have also a greatly reduced number of moving parts, and so can be more compact and significantly lighter, they are also more powerful. Due to this fact, two-stroke engines are used as a source of energy of the biggest vessels such tankers and containers. On the other hand, they create more noise as well as more pollutions (Fig. 3.2). The comparison between the four-stroke and two-stroke diesel engine is presented in Table 3.2. Depending on the operational location and type of the ship, different four-stroke engines with desired parameters are used. Main applications of two-stroke diesel engines are presented below [18].

Tanker: Such ships are currently used to transport a vast variety of products such as chemicals, fresh water, wine and molasses. Modern tankers vary in size from smaller, local, coastal tankers to ULCCs (very large crude carriers), some of the largest vessels found sailing the oceans. Many modern tankers are designed for a specific cargo and a specific route with draft typically limited by harbour depth and/or the depth of straits along the preferred shipping route. Gen-sets can play a vital role as cargoes with the high vapour pressure at ambient temperatures may require pressurized tanks or vapour-recovery systems, while heaters may be required to maintain heavy crude oil, residual fuel, asphalt, wax, or molasses in a fluid state for offloading. Tankers frequently sail in environmentally sensitive areas, hence emission requirements (NO_x, SO_x, particulate matter) are important factors when choosing the main driver.

MAN Diesel & Turbo offers two-stroke engines for all tanker sizes that meet strict safety requirements. It is required to have exhaust gas cleaning systems such as SCR for IMO Tier III-compliance (NO_x) and scrubbers for SO_x reduction. Modern auxiliary engines run on the same high-viscosity fuel grades as the main engines to maximize economy.

Bulker: Modern bulk carriers prioritize capacity, safety, efficiency and durability and they often demand cost-efficient propulsion systems with low first-costs. Bulk carriers frequently sail in environmentally sensitive areas (ECA), thus emission requirements (NO_x, SO_x, particulate matter) are important factors while choosing the main driver. Bulk carriers require various types of propulsion systems in accordance with all the bulk carrier sizes – from single-hole mini-bulkers to mammoth ore ships. Modern auxiliary engines run on the same high-viscosity fuel grades as the main engines to maximize economy. It is expected to have the exhaust gas cleaning systems such as SCR for IMO Tier III-compliance (NO_x) and scrubbers for SO_x reduction to comply with IMO Tier III emission regulations and their sulphur limits.

Container: Containerization has greatly reduced the expense of international trade and increased its throughput, especially in relation to consumer goods and commodities. As of today, some

Table 3.2. The comparison between the four-stroke and two-stroke diesel engines [18]

	Four-stroke engine	Two-stroke engine
Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ More torque – In general, four-stroke engines always make extra torque than two-stroke engines at low rpm. Although the two-stroke ones give higher torque at higher rpm but it has a lot to do with fuel efficiency. ✓ More fuel efficiency – four-stroke engines have greater fuel efficiency than two-stroke ones because fuel is consumed once every four strokes. ✓ Less pollution – As power is generated once every four strokes and also as no oil or lubricant is added to the fuel, the four-stroke engine produces less pollution. ✓ More durability – We all know that more the engine runs, quicker it wears out. Two-stroke engines are designed for high rpm. If an engine can go for 10,000 rpm before it wears out; the four-stroke engine with 100 rpm will run for 100 min while two-stroke engine which has a higher rpm of 500 and will run for only 20 min. ✓ No extra addition of oil – Only the moving parts need lubrication intermediately. No extra oil or lubricant is added to fuel. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Simple design and construction – It does not have valves. It simply has inlet and outlet ports which makes it simpler. ✓ More powerful – In the two-stroke engine, every alternate stroke is power stroke unlike four-stroke one in which power is delivered once every four strokes. This gives a significant power boost. Also, the acceleration will be higher and power delivery will be uniform due to the same reason. ✓ The position doesn't matter – two-stroke engine can work in any position as lubrication is done through the means of fuel (as the fuel passes through the whole cylinder and crankcase).
Disadvantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Complicated design – four-stroke engine has complex valve mechanisms operated and controlled by gears and chain. Also, there are many parts to worry about which makes it harder to troubleshoot. ✓ Less powerful – As power is delivered once every two rotations of the crankshaft (four strokes), hence four stroke is less powerful. ✓ Expensive – A four-stroke engine has much more parts than the two-stroke engine. So it often requires repairs which leads to greater expense. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Less fuel efficiency – For every alternate power stroke, fuel is consumed every alternate stroke. This makes the engine less fuel efficient although it results in uniform power delivery. ✓ Oil addition could be expensive – Two-stroke engines require a mix of oil in with the air-fuel mixture to lubricate the crankshaft, connecting rod and cylinder walls. These oils may empty your pockets. ✓ More pollution – two-stroke engine produces a lot of pollution. The combustion of oil added to the mixture creates a lot of smoke which leads to air pollution. ✓ Wastage of fuel – Sometimes the fresh charge which is going to undergo combustion gets out along with the exhaust gases. This leads to wastage of fuel and also power delivery of the engine is effected. ✓ Improper combustion – The exhaust gases often get trapped inside the combustion chamber. This makes the fresh charge impure. Therefore maximum power does not get delivered because of improper incomplete combustion.

90% of non-bulk cargo worldwide is moved by containers stacked aboard container vessels. Container operators generally demand cost-efficient propulsion systems with low first-costs while significant auxiliary power to operate reefer containers is another key criterion. Container ships frequently sail in environmentally sensitive areas, hence emission requirements (NO_x, SO_x, particulate matter) are important factors when choosing the main driver. It is expected to have the exhaust gas cleaning systems such as SCR for IMO Tier III-compliance (NO_x) and scrubbers for SO_x reduction to comply with IMO Tier III emission regulations and their sulphur limits. Modern auxiliary engines run on the same high-viscosity fuel grades as the main engines to maximize economy.

LNG: According to section 3.1.

Future application: According to MAN Diesel & Turbo Marine Engine IMO Tier II and Tier III Programme 2nd edition 2017, the two-stroke engines are shortly expected to meet the newest strict emission regulations. According to this programme, the two-stroke engines are either [19]:

- Tier II engines complying with IMO Tier II,
- Tier III engines complying with Tier II when operated in Tier II mode and with Tier III when operated in Tier III mode.

There are different parameters defined in MAN Diesel & Turbo Marine Engine IMO Tier II and Tier III Programme 2nd edition 2017 for new two-stroke engines:

- Engine power: The engine brake power is stated in kW, and the power values stated are available up to tropical conditions at sea level, i.e. [19]:

- turbocharger inlet air temperature: 45°C,
- turbocharger inlet air pressure: 1,000 mbar,
- cooling water (sea/fresh) temperature: 32/36°C.

- Specific fuel oil consumption (SFOC): The SFOC is usually represented by the figures of SFOC in relation to the percentage of power which shows the values obtained when the engine and turbocharger are matched to the lowest possible SFOC values while fulfilling the IMO NO_x Tier II or Tier III emission limits. The SFOC is given in g/kWh and it is based on the use of a fuel oil with a lower calorific value (LCV) equal to 42.700 kJ/kg at ISO conditions [19]:

- turbocharger inlet air temperature: 25°C,
- turbocharger inlet air pressure: 1,000 mbar,
- cooling water temperature: 25°C.

Most commercially available HFOs with a viscosity below 700 cSt (7 cm²/s) at 50°C can be used.

- Tolerances: The energy efficiency design index (EEDI) has increased focus on part-load SFOC. Therefore, it is possible to select the SFOC guarantee at a load point in the range from 50% to 100%. It is recommended that the SFOC guarantee point should be limited to the range 50% to 85% for part-load or low-load tuning methods.

All engine design criteria, for example, heat load, bearing load and mechanical stress on the construction, are defined at 100% load, independently of the selected guarantee point. This means that turbocharger matching, engine adjustment and engine load calibration must also be performed at 100% load, independently of the guaranteed point. When choosing an SFOC guarantee at or below 100%, the tolerances, adjustment and calibration at 100% will affect engine running at the lower SFOC guarantee load point. This includes tolerances on measurement equipment, engine process control and turbocharger performance. Consequently, SFOC guarantee tolerances are as follows:

- 5% tolerance for 100-85% engine load,
- 6% tolerance for < 85-65% engine load,
- 7% tolerance for < 65-50% engine load.

- Updated fuel consumption on selected engines: As a result of tests, the fuel consumptions of G95ME-C9.5, G90ME-C10.5, G80ME-C9.5 and S90ME-C10.5 engines have been updated. Figure 3.3 shows an example of the improvement for a Tier II, L1 rated G90ME-C10.5 engine in high-load (HL) optimization:

The fuel consumption for Tier III options and dual fuel engines has also been updated. Similar improvements can be realized with part-load and low-load tuning.

- Turbocharging system: Two-stroke engines can be delivered with MAN, ABB or MHI turbochargers as standard. The SFOC figures given in the two-stroke chapter are based on turbocharging with the best possible turbocharging efficiency generally available, which means 67% for all engines with the 45-cm bore and larger, and 64% for engine bores smaller than 45 cm. Both efficiency figures refer to 100% SMCR (specified maximum continuous rating). Recently we have added exceptions to this rule. Today, the G40ME-C9.5 is available as a high-efficiency application offering all Tier II standard tunings and all Tier III options requiring a high-efficiency turbocharger. The S40ME-B9 and S35ME-B9 type engines are also available as high-efficiency applications offered with high-load tuning and Tier III options with conventional-efficiency turbocharging. Only engine specifications for which an applicable

Fig. 3.3. Improvement of the G90ME-C10.5 engine [19]

high-efficiency turbocharger is available are subject to the firm order. All Tier II engines with high-efficiency (67%) turbochargers can be ordered with lower (conventional) turbocharging efficiency. Utilizing this possibility will result in higher exhaust gas temperatures, lower exhaust gas amounts, and a slight change in SFOC. It is not possible to apply tuning methods (part- or low-load) when making such a conversion.

Table 3.3. EGR-matching concepts

EGR concept	Description
EGRTC	T/C cut-out matching for engines with bores ≥ 80 cm and more than one turbocharger applied
EGRBP	Bypass matching for engines with bores ≤ 70 cm and one high-efficiency turbocharger and for engines with bores ≤ 40 cm and one conventional efficiency turbocharger

- Fuel consumption and optimization: Possibilities for Tier II engines various optimization are available for the MAN B&W type engines. High-load optimization is for the best possible SFOC at 100% engine load. Optimization of SFOC in the part-load range (50-85%) or low-load range (25-70%) requires selection of the exhaust gas bypass (EGB) tuning method. Also, high-pressure tuning (HPT) is available on request for engines. The above tuning methods are available for all SMCR points, but cannot be combined. The SFOC reduction potential of each tuning method at L1 rating can be seen on each individual engine page. In cases where part-load or low-load EGB tuning is applied, and a higher exhaust gas temperature is needed, a solution exists for additional automatic control of the EGB, the so-called economizer energy control (EEC). Forcing an open EGB at loads where the EGB is normally closed results in a higher exhaust gas temperature, but with an SFOC penalty.

Table 3.4. SCR-matching concepts [19]

SGR concept	Description
MAN SCR-HP	High-pressure SCR with a static mixer and SCR reactor installed upstream the turbocharger(s)
MAN SCR-LP	Low-pressure SCR with a static mixer and SCR reactor installed downstream the turbocharger(s)

- Tier III technologies: To ensure compliance with IMO Tier III regulations, one of the two major NO_x reduction technologies must be selected – EGR or SCR (details about this installation in section 4). Which technology is preferred depends on market demands, engine size, other requirements and operational pattern.

MAN B&W S70ME-C8.5

Tier III

Cyl. L₁ kW Stroke: 2,800 mm

5	16,350
6	19,620
7	22,890
8	26,160

Dual Fuel Mode for GI (Methane)

L₁ MEP: 20.0 bar

MAN B&W S70ME-C8.5-GI-EGRTC

L₁ SFOC equivalent gas + pilot fuel (42,700 kJ/kg) [g/kWh]*

	50%	75%	100%
Tier II mode	162.5	164.5	171.0
Tier III mode	170.5	169.0	174.0

L₁ SGC 50,000 kJ/kg (SPOC pilot fuel 42,700 kJ/kg) [g/kWh]

Tier II mode	131.7 (8.3)	135.2 (6.3)	141.6 (5.2)
Tier III mode	138.5 (8.3)	139.0 (6.3)	144.1 (5.2)

MAN B&W S70ME-C8.5-GI-HPSCR

L₁ SFOC equivalent gas + pilot fuel (42,700 kJ/kg) [g/kWh]*

	50%	75%	100%
Tier II mode	162.5	164.5	170.5
Tier III mode	164.0	165.5	171.0

L₁ SGC 50,000 kJ/kg (SPOC pilot fuel 42,700 kJ/kg) [g/kWh]

Tier II mode	131.8 (8.2)	135.3 (6.2)	141.2 (5.1)
Tier III mode	133.1 (8.2)	136.1 (6.2)	141.7 (5.1)

MAN B&W S70ME-C8.5-GI-LPSCR

L₁ SFOC equivalent gas + pilot fuel (42,700 kJ/kg) [g/kWh]*

	50%	75%	100%
Tier II mode	162.5	164.5	170.5
Tier III mode	163.5	165.5	171.5

L₁ SGC 50,000 kJ/kg (SPOC pilot fuel 42,700 kJ/kg) [g/kWh]

Tier II mode	131.8 (8.2)	135.3 (6.2)	141.2 (5.1)
Tier III mode	132.7 (8.2)	136.1 (6.2)	142.1 (5.1)

* Gas fuel LCV (50,000 kJ/kg) is converted to fuel oil LCV (42,700 kJ/kg) for comparison with a fuel oil operated engine.

Fig. 3.4. Sample specification of the new two-stroke engine S70ME-C8.5 [19]

Engine Dimensions

Specifications

Dimensions:	A	B ₁	B ₂	C	H ₁	H ₂	H ₃
mm	1,190	4,390	4,454	1,521	12,550	11,725	11,500

Cylinders:	5	6	7	8
L _{min} mm	7,781	8,971	10,161	11,351

Tier II

Dry mass: t	451	534	605	681
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Tier III

Dry mass (added):		5	6	7	8
EGR	t	15	16	17	18
HP SCR	t	4	5	6	6
LP SCR	t	-	-	-	-

Fig. 3.5. S70ME-C8.5 engine dimensions [19]

All Tier III engines have two operating modes:

- Tier III mode fulfilling the IMO Tier III regulations
- Tier II mode fulfilling the IMO Tier II regulations.

The Tier III technologies are designed for the use of low-sulphur fuels (0-0.1% sulphur) in Tier III mode. This limitation for sulphur content applies to Tier III operation only. In Tier II operation, the engine is in all cases capable of using fuels with a high sulphur content. Tier III designs for use of high-sulphur fuels in Tier III mode are available on request. Fuel consumption guarantees can be given for engines for both Tier II and Tier III mode.

- EGR: Two EGR-matching concepts are available depending on engine type [19]. They are presented in Table 3.3.

For the smallest bore engines, especially with five and six cylinders, the availability of applicable turbochargers makes it difficult to apply EGR. Therefore, SCR is recommended for these engines. SCR-matching concepts are presented in Table 3.4.

The SCR system must be supplied by an approved supplier. For some large-bore engines (bores ≥ 90 cm) with a high cylinder number, SCR-HP is also available.

- Application of high-sulphur fuels and SO_x scrubbers: All two-stroke engines in the MAN Diesel & Turbo marine engine programme are compatible with SO_x scrubbers. A SO_x scrubber installation will increase the back pressure, thereby affecting engine performance. Accordingly, we require that a SO_x scrubber installation does not increase the back pressure by more than 30 mbar at SMCR.

- Waste heat recovery systems: On engines with high-efficiency turbochargers, waste heat can be economically recovered by installing equipment for waste heat recovery (WHR) and matching the engine for WHR. WHR systems are available for both Tier II and Tier III engines. The following types of WHR systems have been approved for application:

Table 3.5. Properties of marine diesel fuels in accordance with ISO-8217 standard

Limit	Parameter	DMX	DMA	DFA	DMZ	DFZ	DMB	DFB
Max.	Viscosity at 40°C [mm ² /s]	5.500	6.000		6.000		11.00	
Min.	Viscosity at 40°C [mm ² /s]	1.400	2.000		3.000		2.000	
Max.	Micro carbon residue at 10% residue [% m/m]	0.30	0.30		0.30		-	
Max.	Density at 15°C [kg/m ³]	-	890.0		890.0		900	
Max.	Micro carbon residue [% m/m]	-	-		-		0.30	
Max.	Sulphur [% m/m]	1.00	1.00		1.00		1.50	
Max.	Water [% V/V]	-	-		-		0.30	
Max.	Total sediment by hot filtration [% m/m]	-	-		-		0.10	
Max.	Ash [% m/m]	0.010	0.010		0.010		0.010	
Min.	Flash point [°C]	43.0	60.0		60.0		60.0	
Max.	Pour point in winter [°C]	-	-6		-6		0	
Max.	Pour point in summer [°C]	-	0		0		6	
Max.	Cloud point in winter [°C]	-16	report		report		-	
Max.	Cloud point in summer [°C]	-16	-		-		-	
Max.	Cold filter plugging point in winter [°C]	-	report		report		-	
Max.	Cold filter plugging point in summer [°C]	-	-		-		-	
Min.	Calculated cetane index	45	40		40		35	
Max.	Acid number [mg KOH/g]	0.5	0.5		0.5		0.5	
Max.	Oxidation stability [g/m ³]	25	25		25		25	
Max.	Fatty acid methyl ester (FAME)	-	-	7.0	-	7.0	-	7.0
Max.	Lubricity, corrected wear scar diameter (wsd 1.4 at 60°C) [µm]	520	520		520		520	
Max.	Hydrogen sulphide [mg/kg]	2.00	2.00		2.00		2.00	
Max.	Appearance	Clear and bright					-	

- power turbines with a power output equal to 3-5% of the engine shaft power at SMCR;
 - power turbines and steam turbines with a power output corresponding to 8-10% of the engine shaft power at SMCR;
 - steam turbine system – with a power output corresponding to 4-6% of the engine shaft power at SMCR;
 - turbochargers with a motor/generator attached to the turbocharger shaft, and with a power output equal to 3-5% of the engine shaft power at SMCR.
- Lubricating oil consumption: The system oil consumption varies according to engine sizes and, operational and maintenance patterns.
- Specific cylinder oil consumption: Alpha ACC (adaptive cylinder-oil control) is the lubrication mode for MAN B&W two-stroke engines that involves lube oil dosing proportional to the engine load and to the sulphur content in the fuel oil being burned. The specific minimum dosage for low-sulphur fuels is set to 0.6 g/kWh. The typical ACC dosage for a BN 100 cylinder oil is 0.3 g/kWh × S%.

Fig. 3.6. The application of piston engines as a marine propulsion

Sample specification of the new two-stroke engine (S70ME-C8.5) is presented in Figs. 3.4, 3.5 and properties of marine diesel fuels in accordance with ISO-8217 standard are presented in Table 3.5 [19]. The application of piston engines as a marine propulsion is presented in Fig. 3.6.

4. CURRENTLY AVAILABLE SO_x/NO_x EMISSION CONTROL SYSTEMS

4.1. SO_x pollution control

Emission of SO₂ is directly proportional to the sulphur content of the fuel. The simplest and the least labour-intensive way to reduce it is to go over to using fuel oil in a low sulphur content. Another possibility, as mentioned before, is to use the SO_x scrubber. There are two different types of such devices [3]:

- wet scrubbers – using a water (fresh/seawater) as the scrubbing medium,
- dry scrubbers – using a dry adsorbent as the scrubbing medium.

Fig. 4.1. Division of currently available wet SO_x scrubbing systems [3]

Wet scrubbers can also be divided into open loop, closed loop and hybrid systems, which is illustrated in Fig. 4.1.

In general, each wet scrubbing system consists of the same basic elements: a scrubber unit (directly contact of water and exhaust gas from one or more combustion unit, typically mounted high up in the ship in or around the funnel), a treatment plant (conditioning of wash-water before discharge overboard), residue handling facility (managing with sludge separated from the washwater), pipes, tanks, monitoring and control systems, various pumps and coolers concerning the scrubbing system configuration. It may be also necessary to include a reheater (lowing the exhaust gas temperature) or demister. Due to highly corrosive washwater, the wet SO_x scrubber system should be constructed of suitable corrosion-resistance materials. The main dimensions of typical scrubber unit, which can be used in maritime industry are presented in Table 4.1 and Fig. 4.2.

Table 4.1. Main dimensions of typical scrubber unit applied in maritime engines exhaust gas treatment system

Dimension	Description	Scrubber unit						
		1 MW	2 MW	4 MW	6 MW	8 MW	11 MW	15 MW
	Exhaust gas mass flow [kg/s]	2.15	4.30	8.60	12.90	17.20	23.65	32.25
A	Vessel diameter [mm]	850	1 350	1 750	2 000	2 500	2 900	3 500
B	Overall length [mm]	1 730	2 240	3 295	3 850	4 660	5 360	6 250
B1	Overall width [mm]	1 250	1 580	1 980	2 240	2 740	3140	3 660
C	Outlet height [mm]	4 020	4 460	4 835	5 810	6 150	6935	8 205
D	Inlet height [mm]	4 670	5 200	7 015	8 495	9 635	10 665	12 130
E	Drain below base [mm]	40	120	150	190	250	315	595
F	Scrubber inlet height [mm]	1 480	1 660	2 050	2 435	2 985	3 330	3 680
X	Difference between bottom part and inlet [mm]	0	0	200	200	250	150	300
S	Distance between support [mm]	690	745	745	790	1 015	1 160	1 260
N1	Inlet nominal bore [mm]	400	600	900	1 100	1 300	1 500	1 700
N2	Outlet nominal bore [mm]	400	600	850	1 000	1 100	1 300	1 600
N3	Drain nominal bore [mm]	150	200	273	400	400	450	500
	Dry weight [tones]	1.2	2.0	2.8	4.1	5.9	7.4	10.4
	Wet weight [tones]	1.5	2.7	3.7	5.4	8.6	11.5	16.9
Hw	Water level [mm]	600	500	435	420	550	580	610
	Water weight [tones]	0.30	0.7	1.0	1.3	2.8	4.1	6.5

Fig. 4.2. Main dimensions of typical scrubber unit applied in maritime engines exhaust gas treatment systems

Wet SO_x scrubber – open loop: This system is accomplished by extraction of water directly from the sea. Thereafter water is contacted with the exhaust gas and discharged back to the sea. There is no recirculation of washwater in this system. The washwater rate in open loop is approximately 45 m³/MWh and removal rate is close to 98% (with full alkalinity water). An open loop wet SO_x scrubbing system is presented in Fig. 4.3. The chemical reactions are the following [20]:

- for SO₂:

- for SO₃:

Conclusion: The high efficiency of SO₂ removal renders that it is possible to use a 3.50% sulphur fuel, which after scrubbing will be an equivalent of 0.10% sulphur fuel [20]. On the other hand, there are several parameters, which should be considered before the decision of using the wet scrubber in the open loop system. First of all, marine's scrubbing and denitration systems are expected to be compatible. NO_x reducing systems usually require a high temperature of activation, close to 300°C. Simultaneously, SO₂ solubility reduces at higher seawater temperatures. For this reason, equipment manufacturers are expected to provide guidance on the maximum sulphur content of fuel that can be consumed by an engine or boiler with a scrubbed exhaust, so that emissions remain within applicable limits, together with any seawater temperature limitations that may apply and, if applicable, the engine's NO_x certification limits. As always, it is also necessary to mix the washwater with the exhaust without making a back-pressure that exceeds the regulations and to reduce the space required for installation, which will decline manufacturing costs.

Fig. 4.3. An open loop wet SO_x scrubbing system [3]

Wet SO_x scrubber – closed loop: This system uses fresh water treated with sodium hydroxide (NaOH) as the scrubbing media. Rather than open loop scrubbing system, the washwater from closed loop after the cleaning is recirculated. The composition of wastewater from scrubber operating in closed loop mode is presented in Table 4.2. The washwater rate in the closed loop is approximately $20 \text{ m}^3/\text{MWh}$ and the washwater discharge is around $0.1 \text{ m}^3/\text{MWh}$. The concentration of typically used NaOH solution is 50% (with 1530 kg/m^3 density at 15°C) which directly appeals to the dosage rate around 15 L/MWh . The chemical reactions are the following [20]:

- for SO_2 :

- for SO_3 :

Table 4.2. The composition of wastewater from scrubber operating in closed loop mode

Wastewater component	Content [% mas.]
Water	> 75
Sulphates	< 25
Sulphite	< 1
Nitrite	< 0.2
Nitrates	< 0.2
Metals as sum	< 0.006
Hydrocarbons as sum C10-C40	< 0.0001

Fig. 4.5. A hybrid SO_x scrubbing system, operating in closed loop mode [3]

Dry SO_x scrubber: This system consists of a scrubber unit (adsorber, which contacts exhaust gas from one or more combustion unit with calcium hydroxide granules), a granule supply silo and screw conveyor (for discharge, positioned at the top and bottom of the absorber)

Fig. 4.6. A dry SO_x scrubber system [3]

Table 4.3. Comparison of different SO_x scrubbing technologies [3, 20, 21]

	Wet (open loop)	Wet (closed loop)	Wet (hybrid)	Dry	Comment
Main components	Scrubber, washwater pumps, washwater piping, washwater treatment equipment, sludge handling equipment	Scrubber, washwater pumps, washwater piping, washwater processing tank, washwater holding tank, sodium hydroxide storage tank, washwater treatment equipment, sludge handling equipment	Scrubber, washwater pumps, washwater piping, washwater processing tank, washwater holding tank, sodium hydroxide storage tank, washwater treatment equipment, sludge handling equipment	Adsorber, fresh granulate hopper, used the granulate hopper, granulate transport system, additional granulate storage (new/used granules)	More complicated systems naturally require more auxiliary devices. While using wet SO _x scrubber systems it is necessary to handle with washwater tanks and accessories as well as with sludges. The hybrid system is more flexible but requires more complex scrubber unit than other installations. Dry systems are less complicated in terms of quantity of necessary apparatus, but they require the granulate transport system and storage.
Weight	30-55 tons (excluding washwater system and treatment equipment)	30-55 tons (excluding washwater system, treatment equipment, washwater processing tank and washwater holding tank)	30-55 tons (excluding washwater system, treatment equipment, washwater processing tank and washwater holding tank)	~200 tons (excluding additional granulate system)	The filled dry scrubber unit for a 20 MW engine is usually heavier than comparable exhaust capacity wet scrubbers. Nonetheless, in reality, the overall weight of both systems may be similar once the washwater systems, such as the processing tank, holding the tank and chemical storage, are taken into account.
Power consumption [% of max. scrubbed engine power]	1-2%	0.5-1%	0.5-2% (depending on whether it is operating in open or closed loop mode)	0.15-0.20%	The washwater flow rate in a closed loop SO _x scrubber is lower ($\approx 20 \text{ m}^3/\text{MWh}$) than in open loop SO _x scrubber ($\approx 45 \text{ m}^3/\text{MWh}$) because the buffering capacity of seawater is less than the buffering capacity of fresh water dosed with sodium hydroxide. Consequently, open loop SO _x scrubbers require larger pumps and have higher power requirements. The power requirement of dry SO _x scrubber systems is mainly related to a screw conveyor hence it is considerably less than for wet SO _x scrubbers.
Operation in fresh water	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Alkalinity or the buffering capacity of seawater is a key parameter for the effective operation of wet open loop SO _x scrubbers (including hybrid SO _x scrubbers when operating in open loop mode). When exhaust gas is mixed with seawater inside the scrubber, sulphur oxides are dissolved, increasing the acidity and lowering the pH of the washwater. Alkalinity is a measure of the ability to resist changes in pH; in seawater, alkalinity is naturally provided by bicarbonates, carbonates, borates and anions of other 'salts' in more minor quantities. Areas within the Baltic Sea do not have sufficient alkalinity to support the operation of wet open loop SO _x scrubbers. Closed loop wet SO _x scrubbers (including hybrid SO _x scrubbers operating in closed loop mode) and dry SO _x scrubbers do not use seawater as their scrubbing medium; therefore they are unaffected by the properties of the water the ship is operating in. The energy consumption will affect any operational energy efficiency key performance indicators that include actual energy consumption of auxiliary systems

Table 4.3. Contd.

	Wet (open loop)	Wet (closed loop)	Wet (hybrid)	Dry	Comment
Operation without discharge to sea	No	For a limited time depending on the size of the washwater holding tank	For a limited time depending on the size of washwater holding tank	Yes	The high washwater discharge rate ($\approx 45 \text{ m}^3/\text{MWh}$) of open loop systems (and hybrid systems in open loop mode) means that when operating they have to discharge washwater into the sea continuously. The much lower discharge rate ($0.1 \text{ m}^3/\text{MWh}$) of closed loop systems (and hybrid systems operating in closed loop mode) means that it is possible to retain washwater to be discharged on board for a limited period of time. Dry SO_x scrubbers have no discharges to sea. Being able to operate in zero discharge mode is ideal for areas where there is sensitivity to washwater discharges, such as ports and estuaries.
Scrubbing chemical consumable	No consumable	Sodium hydroxide solution	Sodium hydroxide solution (while operating in closed loop mode)	Calcium hydroxide granules	Due to highly corrosive washwater, the wet SO_x scrubber system should be constructed of suitable corrosion-resistance materials, which can generate additional costs. Sodium hydroxide is corrosive to glass, aluminium, tin, bronze, brass, zinc and mild steel at over 50°C . The restrict regulations about the usage of NaOH are expected to be met by appropriate personal protective equipment in accordance with material safety data sheets. Calcium hydroxide is strong alkali and it is classed as harmful to eye and skin. The regulations about the usage of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ are expected to be met in accordance with material safety data sheets, but calcium hydroxide is significantly less hazardous than 50% aqueous NaOH solution used in wet systems.
Compatibility with the waste heat recovery system	Yes, provided the scrubber is installed after the waste heat recovery system	Yes, provided the scrubber is installed after the waste heat recovery system	Yes, provided the scrubber is installed after the waste heat recovery system	Yes. Can be placed before or after the waste heat recovery system	All wet SO_x scrubbers significantly cool the exhaust gas and are therefore not suitable for installation before a waste heat recovery unit. For the same reason, it would not be possible to install a wet SO_x scrubber before an SCR system unless a reheater was fitted after the wet scrubber to raise the exhaust gas temperature back up to around 300°C – the temperature required for SCR systems to work effectively. Dry SO_x scrubbers do not cool the exhaust gas so they are suitable for installation before both waste heat recovery units and SCR systems.
Compatibility with SCR system	No, unless a reheater is fitted after the wet scrubber to raise the exhaust gas temperature	No, unless a reheater is fitted after the wet scrubber to raise the exhaust gas temperature	No, unless a reheater is fitted after the wet scrubber to raise the exhaust gas temperature	Yes	
Compatibility with EGR system	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	-
Particulate matter removal	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	SO_x scrubbers can be an effective means of reducing PM both indirectly by removal of SO_x and by direct mechanical cleaning when particles come into direct contact with either washwater or chemical granules. SO_x scrubber manufacturers typically claim between 70% and 90% removal rates. The sulphates, which make a significant contribution to PM, are formed post-combustion in the exhaust plume. Oxidation of SO_2 , followed by further oxidation and condensation processes, contributes to the growth of complex particles after the cylinder and the majority of sulphates form in reactions after release from the stack.

and a scrubber control and emission monitoring system. This kind of scrubber typically works at exhaust temperatures between 240°C and 450°C. Calcium hydroxide granules are between 2 mm and 8 mm in diameter with a very high surface area to maximize the masses exchange. The rate of calcium hydroxide granules is approximately 40 kg/MWh and, based on a density of 800 kg/m³, the volume of granulate would be 0.05 m³/MWh. A dry SO_x scrubbing system is presented in Fig. 4.6. The chemical reactions are the following [20]:

- for SO₂:

The sulphite is then oxidized and hydrated in the exhaust stream to form calcium sulphate dihydrate or gypsum:

- for SO₃:

Conclusion: The efficiency of SO₂ removal renders that it is possible to use a 2.70% sulphur fuel, which after scrubbing will be an equivalent of 0.10% sulphur fuel [20]. Electrical power consumption is lower than for wet systems at approximately 0.15-0.20% of the power of the engine being scrubbed. During the dry scrubbing, it is no necessity to have the washwater treatment system and its associated tankage, instrumentation, pipework and controls. However, there is a requirement for used granules storage before disposal ashore.

Calcium hydroxide is strong alkali and it is classed as harmful to eye and skin. The regulations about the usage of Ca(OH)₂ are expected to be met in accordance with material safety data sheets, but calcium hydroxide is significantly less hazardous than 50% aqueous NaOH solution used in wet systems. The main problem is to keep granules dry and away from contact with acids. The dry scrubbing is ideally suited for use in conjunction with SCR NO_x reducing system, which, as mentioned, requires hot exhaust gas to gain an operating temperature of above 300°C. Comparison of different SO_x scrubbing technologies is presented in Table 4.3.

Table 4.4. Major types of wet scrubbers [22-25]

General category of scrubbers	Particle capture mechanism	Liquid collection mechanism	Specific types of scrubbers
Performed-spray	impaction	droplets	spray towers, cyclonic spray towers, vane-type cyclonic towers, multiple-tube cyclones
Packed-bed scrubbers	impaction	sheets, droplets (moving-bed scrubbers)	standard packed-bed scrubbers, fibre-bed scrubbers, moving-bed scrubbers, cross-flow scrubbers, grid packed scrubbers
Tray-type scrubbers	impaction, Brownian diffusion	droplets, jets and sheets	perforated-plate, impingement-plate scrubbers, horizontal impingement-plate (baffle) scrubbers
Mechanically aided scrubbers	impaction	droplets and sheets	wet fans
Venturi and orifice scrubbers (gas atomized scrubbers)	inertial impaction, Brownian diffusion	droplets	standard venturi scrubbers; variable-throat venturi scrubbers; flooded disc, plump bob, movable blade, radial flow; variable rod orifice scrubbers

Scrubbing equipment and key operating parameters – wet scrubbing: There are many different types of wet scrubber vessels. The type of scrubber selected is based on factors such as the gas temperature, pollutants to be removed, space available and desired efficiency. Some types of scrubbers are mainly designed to remove particulate pollutants (e.g. venture scrubbers) and others are designed to mostly remove gaseous pollutants or soluble particulates (e.g. packed towers and tray towers). Spray chambers are often added ahead of the scrubbers to condition the gas by saturating the gas stream, by cooling the gas stream via evaporative cooling or by removing larger particulates. Examples of various categories of wet scrubbers and related types of scrubbers are presented in Table 4.4.

Wet scrubbing is a two-step process, the first step being the capture of the gas stream contaminants in the liquid and the second step being the separation of the scrubbing liquid droplets from the gas stream after leaving the scrubber. This step is important in the ultimate collection of pollutants because poor liquid separation will cause reentrainment of the droplets containing pollutant. There are four basic types of liquid entrainment separators (demisters): mesh-pad, chevron, centrifugal and cyclonic. The mesh-pad and chevron types utilize inertial impaction of the liquid droplets to cause their agglomeration and removal. The centrifugal and cyclonic types utilize centrifugal inertia to collect the liquid droplets. Different types of demisters are presented in Fig. 4.7.

Fig. 4.7. Liquid entrainment separators [23]

A wet scrubbing system could contain more than one different type of scrubber. A typical air pollution control system for a hazardous waste incinerator, for example, might contain a spray chamber or quench chamber to cool and saturate the exhaust gases as they leave the incinerator.

Fig. 4.8. Simple spray tower (left) and cyclonic spray tower (right) [23]

A venturi scrubber would follow the spray chamber to remove most of the particulates before the gas stream enters a packed column for gaseous contaminant removal. Liquid entrainment separators would follow both venturi scrubber and packed column to remove the water droplets and their contained pollutants before going to the next air pollution control stage. In most of these systems, an included draft fan follows the air pollution controls to pull the gases through the control system and force the cleaned exhaust gases through the stack. Different types of scrubbers are presented in Figs. 4.8-4.10.

Fig. 4.9. Fixed throat venturi scrubber (left) and packed-bed scrubber (right) [23]

Gas and vapour collection in wet scrubber air pollution control devices is achieved by adsorption. The process of absorption refers to the contacting of the mixture of gases with a liquid so that part of one or more of the constituents of the gas will dissolve in the liquid. The necessary

Fig. 4.10. Movable blade venturi (left), plumb bob venturi (left, middle), radial flow venturi (right, middle), flooded disc venturi (right) [25]

condition for absorption is the solubility of pollutants in the absorbing liquid. The rate of mass transfer of the soluble constituents from the gas to the liquid phase is determined by diffusional processes occurring on each side of the gas-liquid interface. Equilibrium is another important factor to be considered in controlling the operation of absorption systems. The rate at which pollutant will diffuse into an absorbent liquid will depend upon the departure from equilibrium that is maintained. The rate at which the pollutant mass is transferred from one phase to another depends on a so-called mass transfer or rate coefficient, which equates the quantity of mass being transferred with the driving force. As can be expected, this transfer process ceases upon the attainment of equilibrium.

The scrubbing system is composed of exhaust hoods and ducts handling airborne contaminants. Gas pre-treatment equipment may be required for coarse particulate removal and for cooling before the contaminants enter the scrubber vessel. The contaminant-laden droplets are removed by the entrainment separators. The clean gas is then passed through an induced-draft fan and up the stack. Forced-draft fans upstream of the scrubber are also used.

The key operating parameters affecting the pollution collection are the following [22-25]:

- liquid-to-gas ratio,
- pressure drop,
- velocity/gas flow rate,
- temperature,
- particle size distribution (particulate).

The liquid-to-gas flow rate (L/G) is a calculated value, reflecting the liquid recycling rate for every volume of gas cleaned. High L/G ratios are used for high-temperature gas streams and high-grain loadings. If the L/G ratio falls below the design value, collection efficiency will diminish. Typical liquid-to-gas ratios are presented in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5. Typical L/G ratios for wet scrubbers [25]

Scrubber type	L/G ratio [gal/1000 ft ³]
Venturi	5-8
Cyclonic spray tower	5-10
Spray tower	10-20
Impingement-plate	3-5
Packed-bed	1-4

High L/G ratios are required for high-temperature gas streams to prevent pollutant re-entrainment. When the L/G ratio is not sufficient to saturate the gas stream, pollutant-laden droplets reentering the scrubber from recycled liquors will evaporate (evaporative cooling) and leave the previously captured particulate re-entrained in the gas stream. Should this occur, pre-treatment with clean liquor (for quenching) may be required. The quenching stage saturates the gas stream to minimize evaporation in the scrubbing stage.

The pressure drop across the scrubber includes the energy loss across the liquid-gas contacting section and entrainment separator, with the former accounting for most of the pressure loss. A low-pressure drop scrubber ranges from 2 in H₂O to 10 in H₂O, medium from 10 in H₂O to 30 in H₂O and high, 30 in H₂O and above. The higher the pressure drop, the greater the particulate collection efficiency for both particle size and concentration. Typical pressure drops for various types of wet scrubbers are presented in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6. Typical scrubber pressure drops [25]

Scrubber type	Pressure drop [inches water]
Venturi	10-70
Centrifugal (cyclonic) spray	1-3
Spray tower	1-2
Impingement-plate	1-10
Packed-bed	1-10
Wet fan	4-10
Self-induced spray (orifice)	2-20
Irrigated filter (filter bed scrubber)	0.2-3

The collection of most scrubbers depends upon the velocity of the gas stream through the liquid-contacting section of the scrubber vessel. For particulates, the relative velocity between washing liquids (droplets) and particulates is critical to contaminant collection. In the case of high-energy venturi scrubbers, a velocity of 40,000 ft/min can be delivered. Fine droplet size and high density lead to increased removal efficiency.

When a high-temperature gas stream exhaust enters the scrubber, the volumetric flow rate diminishes accordingly (based on the temperature of the scrubber liquid) because the gas is being cooled by the scrubber liquors. When the system flow rate decreases, the resulting relative velocity may not be sufficient to collect the desired amount of particulate and emissions will increase. For a packed tower or tray tower, low or no gas flow might indicate plugged packing in the absorber, fan problems, duct leaks or an increase in liquid flow to the tower. The increased gas flow might indicate a low liquid flow rate, packing failure or a sudden opening of a system damper.

Wet scrubber inlet and outlet temperatures are also key parameters that should be monitored when controlling gas streams with elevated temperatures. An increase in temperature could indicate a failure of the cooling equipment, which would result in decreased pollutant collection efficiency and perhaps damage to the scrubber.

Performance of a scrubber controlling particulate emissions depends on the gas stream particulate size distribution. Efficient collection of submicron contaminants challenges the application of any type of control system. High-energy venturi scrubbers are designed for submicron contaminant collection. Changes in process equipment or operation can change the particle size distribution and, in turn, impact collection efficiency.

SO₂ absorption at an industrial scale in maritime sector is most commonly practised in packed or spray towers, which are often combined with venturi nozzle. In the spray tower, the liquid is sprayed into a gas stream by means of a nozzle which disperses the liquid into a fine

spray drops. The flow may be countercurrent, as in vertical towers with the liquid sprayed downward, or parallel, as in horizontal spray chambers. These devices have the advantage of low-pressure drop for the gas but also have a number of disadvantages. There is a relatively high pumping cost for the liquid, owing to the pressure drop through the spray nozzle. The tendency for entrainment of liquid by the gas leaving is considerable, and mist eliminators will almost always be necessary.

Fig. 4.11. Some random tower packings: (a) Raschig rings, (b) Lessing rings, (c) partition ring, (d) Berl saddle, (e) Intalox saddle, (f) Tellerette, (g) pall ring [23]

Unless the diameter/length ratio is very small, the gas will be fairly thoroughly mixed by the spray and full advantage of countercurrent flow cannot be taken. Ordinarily, however, the diameter/length ratio cannot be made very small since then the spray would quickly reach the walls of the tower and become ineffective as a spray.

Fig. 4.12. Regular or stacked packings: (a) Raschig rings, stacked staggered; (b) double spiral ring; (c) section through expanded-metal-lath packing; (d) wood grids [23]

Fig. 4.13. The schematic diagram of a packed gas absorption tower [23]

A packed tower is essentially a piece of pipe set on its end and filled with inert material or 'tower packing'. Liquid poured into the top of the tower trickles down through the packing, gas pumped into the bottom of the tower flows countercurrently upward. The intimate contact between gas and liquid achieved in this way effects the gas absorption. Analysing the packed tower involves both mass transfer and fluid mechanics. The mass transfer, detailed in the following section, determines the height of the packed tower. This mass transfer is described as molar flows, partly because of the chemical reactions that often occur. The fluid mechanics determines the cross-sectional area of the packed tower. The fluid mechanics is described as mass flows, a consequence of the physics that control the process.

The fluid mechanics in the packed tower is dominated by the inert material in the packed tower. This material can be small pieces dumped randomly or larger structures carefully stacked inside the tower. Random packing is cheaper and more common whereas structured packing is more expensive but more efficient. Different types of packings are presented in Figs. 4.11 and 4.12.

Generally, random packings offer larger specific surface area (and larger gas pressure drop) in the smaller sizes, but they cost less per unit volume in the larger sizes. As a rough guide, packing sizes of 25 mm or larger are ordinarily used for gas rates of 500 ft³/min (0.25 m³/s), 50 mm or larger for gas rates of 2000 ft³/min (1 m³/s). During installation, the packings are poured into the tower to fall random and in order to prevent breakage of ceramic or carbon packings, the tower may first be filled with water to reduce the velocity of fall. The schematic diagram of a packed gas absorption tower is presented in Fig. 4.13.

The regular packings offer the advantages of low-pressure drop for the gas and greater possible fluid flow rates, usually at the expense of more costly installation than random packing.

While using packed gas absorption tower another crucial issue is an adequate initial distribution of the liquid at the top of the packing. This phenomenon is presented in Fig. 4.14.

Fig. 4.14. Liquid distribution and packing irrigation: (a) inadequate, (b) adequate [23]

As dry packing is completely ineffective for mass transfer, various devices are used for liquid distribution. Spray nozzles generally result in too much entrainment of liquid in the gas to be useful. In the small tower, it is possible to use a ring of perforated pipe. For larger diameters of distributor, many other arrangements are available. It is generally considered necessary to provide at least five points of introduction of liquid for every 1 ft² (0.1 m²) of tower cross-section for the large tower ($d \geq 4$ ft (1.2 m)) and a greater number for smaller diameters. In the case of random packings, the packing density, i.e. the number of packing pieces per unit volume, is ordinarily less in the immediate vicinity of the tower walls and this leads to a tendency of the liquid to segregate toward the walls and the gas to flow in the centre of the tower (channelling). This tendency is much less pronounced when the diameter of the individual

packing pieces is smaller than at least one-eighth of the tower diameter, but it is recommended that, if possible, the ratio 1:15. Even so, it is customary to provide for redistribution of the liquid at intervals varying from 3 times to 10 times the tower diameter, but at least every 6 m or 7 m. Knitted mesh packings placed under a packing support make good redistributors.

Another important parameter to go over is to use liquid flows that are high enough to avoid channelling and achieve loading. It is also expected to use gas flows that are low enough to avoid flooding. Such calculation can be determined using proper correlations for estimating tower cross-sectional area. The example is presented in Fig. 4.15.

Fig. 4.15. Correlation for estimating tower cross-sectional area: gas flux G' (given in $\text{lb}/\text{ft}^3/\text{s}$), the densities ρ_G and ρ_L (given in lb/ft^3), the velocity μ is that of the liquid (expressed in cP), Ψ is the ratio of the density of water to the density of the liquid, the gravitational constant g_C is 32.2 and the packing factor F is roughly inversely proportional to the packing's size. Values for F for common packings can be found in the literature [23]

Scrubbing equipment and key operating parameters – dry scrubbing: This process involves the separation of a substance from one phase, accomplished by the accumulation of that substance at the surface of another phase. Two types of adsorption are possible. The first, physisorption, is a physical process that occurs below 200°C . The material is adsorbed due to molecular interactions between the adsorbent and the adsorbate. The typical heat of physisorption is 5-10 kcal/mol. The second type of adsorption, chemisorption, is a chemical process where the adsorbent adheres to the adsorbate through a chemical bond and that is the phenomenon typically used during the onboard dry scrubbing. Adsorption occurs due to the formation of chemical compounds. Chemisorption bonds can be weak, ranging from 15-40 kcal/mol, or strong, which can be greater than 50 kcal/mol. The dry scrubbing process is accomplished in column contact adsorbers, which can operate as a fixed bed, or as a moving or pulsed bed. Fixed bed operation is the oldest form of column contact adsorption. A bed of adsorbent is held in place inside the column, and the gas to be treated flows over, through and around it. The bed must be taken offline to replace or regenerate the used granules. In a moving or pulsed bed adsorber, untreated gas enters the adsorber from the bottom and flows up the column. At the same time, fresh adsorbent enters the adsorber from the top of the column and exits out the bottom. The exhausted adsorbent is continually removed, while fresh adsorbent is continually added, allowing for more efficient operation. Under fixed bed operation, adsorption columns may be arranged in series or parallel and may be run in either up flow or down flow modes. Pulsed bed operations are restricted to the up flow mode of operation. Additional equipment is required to recycle the adsorbent, which allows for a more efficient operation. In general, smaller adsorbents have a larger surface area and allow for more contact between the packing and adsorbate than larger adsorbents. Therefore, small adsorbents are desirable and enhance the

Fig. 4.16. Fixed bed adsorbers

adsorption rate. However, if adsorbent particles are too small they may restrict the proper flow of fluid through the column. Various kind of contact columns are presented in Figs. 4.16 and 4.17.

Fig. 4.17. Pulsed bed (left) and moving (fluidized) bed (right) adsorbers [23]

While considering the adsorption, there are many key parameters, which can have a significant influence on the process efficiency. Certain general properties of adsorbents are involved in all adsorber design calculations. The necessary properties are as follows [22, 23, 26, 27]:

- isotherms (or other equilibrium data),
- densities and void fractions,
- kinetics,
- fluid-to-particle mass transfer coefficient,
- pressure drop,
- temperature,
- nature of adsorbent.

Isotherms: Adsorption equilibrium data are commonly gathered at a fixed temperature and plotted or tabulated as capacity or loading versus the fluid-phase concentration (or partial pressure for gases and vapours). In that format, the data comprise an isotherm. As mentioned earlier, adsorption capacity governs the capital cost because it dictates the amount of adsorbent required, which also fixes the volume of the adsorber vessels. Figure 4.18 shows classifications suggested by Brunauer, Deming and Teller (1940).

Fig. 4.18. Isotherm classifications (1940) [23]

Types I, II, and IV represent ‘favourable’ equilibrium (concave downwards), while types III and V represent ‘unfavourable’ equilibrium (concave upwards). Type VI has two regions that are favourable and two that are unfavourable. Furthermore, types IV and V exhibit hysteresis, which occurs when desorption occurs along a different path than adsorption, e.g. as a result of liquid-filled pores, and implies that uptake and release may be slow. For all that, only type I of adsorbents, over the range of relevant conditions, are generally suited to cyclic applications.

Linear forms of the isotherm models are widely adopted to determine the isotherm parameters or the most fitted model for the adsorption system due to the mathematical simplicity. The linear forms of the Langmuir, Freundlich and Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm models are given in Table 4.7.

Densities and void fractions: Three densities are relevant: bulk, particle, and solid, represented by q_B , q_P , and q_S , respectively. Likewise, there are four pertinent void fractions, ϵ_B , ϵ_P , ϵ_S , and ϵ . The first three have the same associations as the densities having the same subscripts. The last one, ϵ , is the overall void fraction in the bed of adsorbent. They are related as [27]:

Table 4.7. Linear forms of the isotherm models [28]

Isotherm models	Linear form
Langmuir	$(I) \frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{q_m \cdot K_L} + \frac{C_e}{q_m}$ $(II) \frac{1}{q_e} = \left[\frac{1}{q_m \cdot K_L} \right] \cdot \frac{1}{C_e} + \frac{1}{q_m}$ $(III) q_e = q_m - \left[\frac{1}{K_L} \right] \cdot \frac{q_e}{C_e}$ $(IV) \frac{q_e}{C_e} = K_L \cdot q_m - K_L \cdot q_e$
Freundlich	$\ln q_e = \ln KF + \frac{1}{n} \cdot \ln C_e$
Dubinin-Radushkevich	$\ln q_e = \ln q_s - K_D \cdot \varepsilon^2$

$$q_B = (1 - \varepsilon_B) q_P = (1 - \varepsilon_B)(1 - \varepsilon_P) q_S = (1 - \varepsilon) q_S$$

The bed or bulk density is the mass of adsorbent in a specific volume. This can be measured simply using a graduated cylinder. Particle density is the mass of adsorbent per volume occupied by the particle. This is accurately and easily measured for true cylindrical pellets and beads, but is more difficult for distorted shapes and granular materials, though proprietary methods exist for obtaining accurate values even for those. Solid density is the mass of the adsorbent per volume occupied by the particle, but with the pores deducted. It is measured by immersing a known amount of adsorbent in a liquid of known density and known total volume, then measuring the total mass. In this case, the characteristics of the liquid may dramatically affect the resulting value, because the liquid molecules may or may not be able to penetrate certain pores in a reasonable time due to steric reasons or surface tension. The greater the fraction of pores penetrated, the greater the apparent solid density. Densities and void fractions are important because the most isotherm data are published as loading per unit mass, which is fine for determining the total adsorbent cost since prices are quoted per unit mass. Conversely, to determine the vessel dimensions from the necessary amount of adsorbent, or vice versa, q_B is required. For pressure drop calculations, the relevant void fraction is ε_B since the fluid in the pores of the adsorbent is usually considered to be immobile. In contrast, for material balance equations, the fluid in the pores of the adsorbent cannot be ignored, so the relevant void fraction is ε .

Fluid-to-particle mass transfer coefficient: The fluid-to-particle mass transfer coefficient (k) is mostly governed by the fluid properties (density, ρ , viscosity, μ , and diffusivity, D_{AB}) and superficial velocity ($v_s = Q/A_{cs}$, where Q is the volumetric flow rate and A_{cs} is the cross-sectional area of the empty bed). Generally, a large value of k is good, but not at the expense of high velocity v_s , not because of pumping or compression costs, but because the time of exposure is inversely proportional to velocity. Thus, the faster the fluid is flowing, the less time the adsorbent has to respond.

Pressure drop: Most adsorbers are designed to operate with the relatively low-pressure drop, because large particles are used whenever possible, and because the velocity is typically low to allow equilibration of the fluid with the adsorbent. In addition, a small L/d_{bed} (length/diameter) leads to the low-pressure drop. Conversely, achieving good flow distribution and low dead volume implies a large L/d_{bed} . Generally, pipes, valves, and fittings pose as much of a flow restriction as the pressure drop in the bed of adsorbent.

Kinetics: Mass transfer kinetics is a catch-all term related to intraparticle mass transfer resistance. It is important because it controls the cycle time of a fixed bed adsorption process. Fast kinetics implies a sharp breakthrough curve, while slow kinetics leads to a distended breakthrough curve. The effect of a distended breakthrough curve can be overcome by adding adsorbent at the product end, or by increasing the cycle time (which reduces the throughput per unit of adsorbent). Both of these options increase the amount of adsorbent required. To compensate for slow diffusion, it is also possible to use small particles, but there is a corresponding sacrifice due to increased pressure drop.

Temperature: Since adsorption is an exothermic process, the concentration of adsorbed gas decreases with increasing temperature.

Nature of adsorbents: Both the chemical and physical properties of the adsorbent must be considered. Chemical properties that influence on adsorbent design include the degree of ionization of the surface, functional groups present on the surface, and the degree to which these chemical properties vary with process parameters and by contact with the gas. Adsorbent solids are usually used in granular form, varying in size from roughly 12 mm in diameter to as small as 50 μm . The solids must possess certain engineering properties depending upon the application to which they are put. If they are used in a fixed bed through which a liquid or gas is to flow, for example, they must not offer too great pressure drop for flow nor must they easily be carried away by the flowing stream. They must have adequate strength and hardness so as not to be reduced in size during handling or crushed in supporting their own weight in beds of the required thickness. If they are to be transported frequently in and out of bins, they should be free-flowing. Large surface per unit weight seems essential to all useful adsorbents (100 m^2/g)

Table 4.8. General adsorber design considerations [27]

Basic adsorbent properties	Application considerations	Equipment/flowsheet
<p>A. Isotherm data</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. uptake/release measurements 2. hysteresis observed 3. pre-treatment conditions 4. ageing upon multiple cycles 5. multicomponent effects <p>B. Mass transfer behaviour</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. interface character 2. intraparticle diffusion 3. film diffusion 4. dispersion <p>C. Particle characteristics</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. porosity 2. pore size distribution 3. specific surface area 4. density 5. particle size distribution 6. particle shape 7. abrasion resistance 8. crush strength 9. composition/stability 10. hydrophobicity 	<p>A. Operating conditions</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. flow rate 2. feed and product concentrations 3. pressure/temperature 4. desired recovery 5. cycle time 6. contaminants <p>B. Regeneration technique</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. thermal: steam/hot fluid/kiln 2. chemical: acid/base/solvent 3. pressure shift 4. regenerant/adsorbate recovery or disposal <p>C. Energy requirements</p> <p>D. Adsorbent life</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. attrition/swelling 2. ageing/fouling 	<p>A. Contactor type</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. fixed: axial/radial flow 2. pulsed/fluidized bed <p>B. Geometry</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. number of beds 2. bed dimensions 3. flow distribution 4. dead volumes <p>C. Column internals</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. bed support/ballast 2. flow distribution 3. insulation <p>D. Miscellaneous</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. instrumentation 2. materials of construction 3. safety/maintenance 4. operation, start-up, shut-down

to over 2000 m²/g). Particularly, in the case of gas adsorption, the significantly surface is not the gross surface of the granular particles which are ordinarily used but the very much larger surface of the internal pores of particles. The pores are usually very small, sometimes of the order of a few molecular diameters in width, but their large number provides an enormous surface for adsorption.

The general adsorber design considerations are presented in Table 4.8.

4.2. NO_x pollution control

There are different types of nitrogen oxides, existing in the environment: N₂O, NO, NO₂, N₂O₃, N₂O₄, NO₃, and N₂O₅, but the abbreviation NO_x usually regards nitrogen monoxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), which are considered toxic. Approximately 95% of NO_x emitted from incineration process is insoluble and non-reactive NO and 5% – NO₂. NO is less toxic, notwithstanding it is also unstable but it reacts readily with oxygen through photochemical oxidation to form NO₂. These oxides are formed in the cylinder during combustion in two different ways:

- Thermal NO_x – the main mechanism by which NO_x is produced. Nitrogen oxides are formed in high-temperature reactions between N₂ and O₂ in the charge air (this process depends on temperature, available oxygen and exposure time of the combustion gases to high temperature).
- Fuel NO_x – nitrogen oxides are formed through the oxidation of the nitrogen compounds predominantly contained in residual fuel oils and biofuels (this process depends on the available oxygen, the quantity of fuel-bound nitrogen and, to less extent, combustion temperature and the nature of the nitrogen compounds).

Fig. 4.19. NO_x abatement techniques [29, 30]

Dealing with the emission of nitrogen oxides involves different ways of their reduction. There are various methods for reducing NO_x emissions (Fig. 4.19), depending on cost and effectiveness (Table 4.9). It is possible to distinguish [3, 31]:

- Primary NO_x control – aims to reduce the formation of nitric oxide at the source. It may be achieved through engine design and operational adjustments of parameters and components such as fuel injection (pressure, timing, rate, nozzle configuration), valve timing, charge air (temperature, pressure) and compression ratio. Other at-engine measures can reduce local temperatures and oxygen content in the combustion zone through various wet technologies: water-in-fuel (WIF), fuel water emulsion (FWE), direct water injection to the combustion

space (DWI), water sprays into the charge air (humid air motor – HAM) or scavenging air moistening (SAM). They can be only used to meet Tier II limits. The nature of such processes can also leads to the large power losses.

- Post-combustion abatement – exhaust gas is treated to remove NO_x. The most commonly used method is the selective catalytic reduction (SCR). Other ways such as selective non-catalytic reduction (SNCR), exhaust gas recirculation (EGR), non-thermal plasma (NTP) and lean NO_x traps (LNTs) have been also investigated by scientists.

Table 4.9. The NO_x reduction potential of different methods [29]

NO _x abatement techniques	NO _x reduction
Alternative fuels	50-60%
Emulsified fuel – water addition	50-60%
Basic IEM – slide fuel valves	20%
Injection timing retardation	30%
Compression ratio modification	10-30%
Injection system modification	30%
Scavenge/charge air cooling	14%
Scavenge/charge air pressure increase	10-40%
Direct water injection	40-60%
Humid air motor	70-80%
Exhaust gas recirculation	80-98%
Selective catalytic reduction	80-99%

Selective catalytic reduction: NO_x is converted into nitrogen and water by spraying urea or ammonia into the gases before they pass through a catalytic converter. This installation is able to reduce NO_x emissions by 80-90% to below 2 g/kWh. Reduction costs are generally below 600 EUR/ton of NO_x reduced, lower if the equipment can be installed while the ship is being built [31]. When retrofitted, SCR system replaces the exhaust silencers. SCR systems are commonly fitted to four-stroke medium-speed engines. To date, a very small number of two-stroke engines have been equipped with SCR systems, but it is planned to be done en masse

Fig. 4.20. SCR flowchart [21]

Fig. 4.21. SCR NO_x reducing system – Yara Marine Technologies [32]

for MAN Diesel & Turbo marine engines [3, 21]. The SCR NO_x reducing system is presented in Figs. 4.20 and 4.21. The chemical reactions are as follows:

- Urea decomposition before the catalyst:

- NO_x reduction at the catalyst:

Reaction (4.18) shows the main SCR reaction as nitric oxide dominates in the exhaust. The reaction (4.19) occurs at the fastest rate up to the NO₂: NO ratio of 1:1. Nevertheless, at higher ratios, the excess NO₂ reacts slowly – reaction (4.20).

Fig. 4.22. Dependence between the minimum temperature required for the catalyst and the sulphur content in fuel

SCR NO_x reduction system usually consists of a pumping unit (for transfer of urea solution from storage), a reactor housing containing replaceable catalyst blocks, a urea dosing unit, a mixing duct with urea injection point, a soot/ash cleaning and control systems. If there is a necessity to fit the SCR system to two-stroke low-speed engines it is also required to bypass the reactor during various engine operating modes. The position of the reactor containing the

catalyst is related to the exhaust temperature. That is the reason for installing marine SCR systems on four-stroke engines, as there is a sufficiently high exhaust temperature. The recommended temperature is over 300°C, but below 500°C to prevent thermal damage to the catalyst. Dependence between the minimum temperature required for the catalyst and the sulphur content in fuel is shown in Fig. 4.22.

It is possible to run at lower temperatures, but only after the reducing of the sulphur content in the fuel. Another crucial issue is to completely mix urea with the exhaust gas before entering SCR reactor. A typically used urea's concentration is a 40% solution, which is injected as a fine spray into the mixing duct before the catalyst by means of compressed air. The amount of NH₃ injected into the exhaust gas is controlled by a process computer dosing the NH₃ in proportion to the NO_x produced by the engine as a function of the engine load. The relationship between the NO_x produced and the engine load is measured during test runs on the engine testbed. The relationship obtained is programmed in the process computer and used for the feed-forward control of the NH₃ dosage. The ammonia dosage is subsequently adjusted for bias by a feedback system on the basis of the measured NO_x outlet signal [31].

Fig. 4.23. SCR system layout [21]

As the effective dispersion of the urea in the exhaust stream is pivotal to efficient SCR performance, suitable injection nozzles, atomizing air, high-pressure injection (typically 25 bar), duct design, or a combination of all four are required. The main reason for using urea instead of ammonia is that urea is classed as non-hazardous and can be stored in existing tanks if epoxy-coated whereas ammonia is both toxic and corrosive. The catalysts used in typical marine SCR system are made up of porous titanium dioxide (TiO₂), vanadium pentoxide (V₂O₅) or tungsten trioxide (WO₃) [3, 31]. Figure 4.23 shows the actual system layout of the 6S50MC engine [21] and Table 4.10 presents the SCR current reference list for MC type engines [17].

Table 4.10. SCR reference list for MC type engines [17]

No	Engine	Application	Function	Efficiency
1	6S50MC	ship	NO _x reduction	93-95%
2	6S50MC	ship	NO _x reduction	93-95%
3	6S50MC	ship	NO _x reduction	93-95%
4	6S50MC	ship	NO _x reduction	93-95%
5	9K80MC-GI-S	power plant	NO _x reduction	up to 98%
6	4L35MC-S	power plant	NO _x reduction	> 93%
7	2x7K60MC-S	power plant	NO _x reduction	> 93%
8	6S35MC	ship	NO _x reduction	> 93%

High-efficiency turbochargers have to be used. The measured exhaust gas temperature is slightly higher than for engines without SCR system because of the ammonia/urea heat release in the SCR process. The SCR reactor is designed as a semi-rectangular pressure vessel for horizontal or vertical installation and flow. As an example, the main dimensions (excluding support structure and insulation) for a 11K90MC engine are presented in Table 4.11.

Table 4.11. Main dimensions of 11K90MC engine [21]

Dimension	Value
Diameter [m]	2.4
Height [m]	4.5
Length [m]	15
Weight, including catalyst [tons]	42

The design and dimensions of an SCR reactor are influenced by the exhaust gas flow, the exhaust gas temperature window, and the NO_x reduction rate. The optimum and most common

Fig. 4.24. SCR configurations [17]

solution, therefore, is that the SCR reactor is tailor-made for a specific installation and it is, of course, more convenient to build-in the SCR during the construction of the ship. Retrofit is also possible. The space requirement for an SCR unit in the engine room is considerable, on top of which the piping and the mixer between the engine and the SCR catalyst also require a lot of space, so the designer’s task is to make the SCR system as compact as possible while, at the same time, ensuring easy access for maintenance and operation. As can be seen in Fig. 4.24 there are a number of alternative designs of SCR reactors. Location of the SCR module in the four-stroke engine and two-stroke engine is presented in Fig. 4.25.

Fig. 4.25. Location of the SCR module in the four-stroke engine (left) and two-stroke engine (right)

If ammonia is used as the medium for denitrification, the tank should be located on deck. In the case of urea, we recommend that a tank in the hull structure be used, to lower the cost. Having such a tank in the hull will also minimize the space requirements, compared with the installation of a tank on deck. If it is not possible to find an appropriate tank on board, the tank could be built into containers.

Table 4.12. Engine performance data [17]

Parameter	Prior to installation of SCR	DeNO _x mode with injection of urea
Engine load	75.8%	77%
Turbocharger	15 600 rpm	15 700 rpm
T/C inlet temperature	440°C	440°C
Scavange air pressure	2.02 barg	2.10 barg
NO _x emission	1 100 ppm	132 ppm (< 2 g/kWh)
Urea consumption	-	62 L/h

As mentioned before, retrofit is also possible and after the test trial, the vessel can operate with reduced NO_x emission. For example, the reduction of NO_x emission for an exemplary

6S35MC engine can be obtained between 40-100% engine load, when running on HFO with a sulphur content of up to 2.4%. Below 40% engine load, the injection of urea is stopped due to low exhaust gas temperatures. The risk of creation of ammonia sulphate is thereby avoided. Performance data are shown in Table 4.12, and the actual system layout is shown in Fig. 4.26.

6S35MC, deNO_x

- 1. SCR reactor
- 2. Turbocharger bypass
- 3. Temperature sensor after SCR
- 4. Large motors for auxiliary blowers
- 5. Urea injector
- 6. SCR bypass
- 7. Temperature sensor before SCR
- 8. Additional flange in exhaust gas receiver

Fig. 4.26. 6S35MC engine with SCR catalytic reactor installed [17]

For the two-stroke engines, too low exhaust gas temperature after the turbine has called for a solution where the SCR may be placed on the high-pressure side of the turbine. The efficiency of NO_x removal in relation to the flue gas temperature is presented in Fig. 4.27.

Fig. 4.27. NO_x removal efficiency in relation to the flue gas temperature

Depending on the engine load, this makes it possible to obtain exhaust gas temperatures that are between approximately 50°C and 175°C, higher than after the turbine. The comparison is presented in Table 4.13.

This means that the SCR system works according to the following: When NO_x reduction is needed (inside ECA), the exhaust gas is guided to the SCR according to the flow direction. When no SCR operation is needed (outside ECA), the exhaust gas is passed directly to the turbine in the turbocharger (T/C) and the SCR is sealed by two valves. Table 4.13 reveals that

Table 4.13. Temperature before and after the turbine (turb.), based on a 6S50ME-C two-stroke diesel engine [19]

Temperature	Use of engine			
	25% load	50% load	75% load	100% load
$T_{amb} = 10^{\circ}\text{C}$				
$T_{in\ turb.}\ [^{\circ}\text{C}]$	299	308	337	395
$T_{out\ turb.}\ [^{\circ}\text{C}]$	245	217	207	221
$T_{gain}\ [^{\circ}\text{C}]$	54	92	130	174

even though the reactor is placed before the turbine, the exhaust gas temperature is still too low at loads below approximately 50%. Therefore, it has been necessary to develop a ‘low load method’, which can be used to increase the exhaust gas temperatures. The cylinder and SCR bypass are shown in Fig. 4.28.

Fig. 4.28. Low-load method to increase exhaust gas temperatures [3]

The cylinder bypass valve (CBV) increases the exhaust gas temperature by reducing the mass of air through the cylinders at a fixed amount of fuel combustion. This means that higher exhaust gas temperatures for the SCR are obtained. Calculations have shown that this method is suitable because the mass flow through the T/C remains almost unchanged. This means that the scavenge air pressure is maintained and thus that the combustion is nearly unaffected. It was also verified that the engine and SCR system was able to meet the IMO Tier III NO_x limits, and the results are presented in Table 4.14.

Table 4.14. NO_x emissions at the four IMO engine load points [21]

	25%	50%	75%	100%	Cycle
Tier III [g/kWh]	2.9	3.1	2.9	2.5	2.8

The table reveals that the SCR system ensures a NO_x cycle value of 2.8 g/kWh, which is well below the IMO Tier III limit of 3.4 g/kWh (reduction of 80%).

Conclusion: This system may reduce the emissions of NO_x by more than 90%, (obligatorily requires comparatively low-sulphur fuel), with the cost-effectiveness of 873.5 \$/ton and SO_x

emissions by 98% with 3115 \$/ton in case of using seawater scrubbing. Researchers have indicated that the urea consumption of SCR system is 8.5% of the consumption of diesel oil, which will surely have a significant influence on the size and weight of installation.

The main challenges for marine SCR applications are sulphur resistance and low-temperature activation. Currently, SCR catalyst mainly relies on $V_2O_5-WO_3-TiO_2$, but V_2O_5 is a kind of highly poisonous material and the active temperature is above 300°C. The mechanism for deposit formation involves an undesirable parallel reaction (to the NO_x conversion) at the catalyst whereby sulphur dioxide in the exhaust is oxidized to sulphur trioxide (SO_3), which can then react with ammonia to form ammonium sulphate and bisulphate. Such a process reduce the effective area and shorten the lifespan of the catalyst, with fuel-related hydrocarbon and particulate matter adding to the fouling. As conditions deteriorate, NO_x reduction is impaired and more unreacted ammonia will slip past the catalyst. Manufacturers recommend minimizing the oxidation of sulphur dioxide with their reduction catalyst materials and by specifying that only fuels with a sulphur content of less than 1.00% should be used. This treatment prevents the formation of ammonium sulphates as well as sulphuric acid. Systems capable of operating with higher sulphur content are possible, but in this case, the higher exhaust temperatures are required. As an alternative to low-sulphur fuel, a SO_x scrubber fitted before the reactor is possible to use. When installed after a wet SO_x scrubber the exhaust gas would require reheating from around 50°C to at least 300°C. No reheat would be required for a dry scrubber. An additional undesirable parallel reaction will take place if calcium is present, resulting in calcium sulphate deposits. SCR catalyst material is extremely sensitive to the presence of sulphur in the fuel and it is also subject to poisoning (chemical attack of the active element of the catalyst), fouling (deposition of material which masks the catalyst, preventing contact between the catalyst surface and the reactants, possible to be seen during a visual inspection) and plugging (which refers to the plugging of the catalyst pores, may not be seen during the visual inspection). Additionally, as pressure drop is a function of the bed length and the catalyst configuration, depositing of fly ash or other solid particles on the catalyst can have a profound effect on the engine performance and the back pressure growth may be observed. In order to minimize the pressure losses, the diameter of SCR reactor can be increased, which is most likely impractical onboard.

SCR system has been used for many years for inland installations, which are characterized by long periods of operation under the constant load. The different nature of marine engines' service has become a challenge for producers of SCR technology.

Onboard, there are two types of engines:

- auxiliary engines (aggregates),
- main engines (vessel's propulsion).

As the aggregate, four-stroke self-ignition engines are usually used. In this case, using of SCR technology is definitely a simpler solution, but it is necessary to take into account the presence of the installation at the ship construction stage. Another solution is to try to place it in the existing ship's engine room. While considering main engines, the installation of SCR system is much more problematic. Propulsion engine operates under variable load conditions, especially while working inside the ECA, where sailing at reduced speed is required and thereby the exhaust gas temperature is too low for the catalysis. It may be also a crucial issue for ammonia or urea dosing systems. SCR technology involves a periodic check of the catalyst efficiency and thereafter there may be a necessity to replace it.

Exhaust gas recirculation: In this technology a proportion of the exhaust from before the turbo-charger is recirculated to the cylinders with the charge air, which allows lowering the oxygen content of the mixture as well as increases its heat capacity. It brings about reduction of peak combustion temperatures and suppresses the formation of thermal NO_x . EGR installation consists of: high-pressure exhaust gas scrubber fitted before the engine turbocharger (used to remove sulphur oxides and particulate matter from the recirculated exhaust and to prevent corrosion and reduce fouling of the EGR system and engine components, typically working in the closed loop mode), a water mist catcher (WMC) to remove entrained water droplets, a cooler to further reduce the temperature of the recirculated gas, a high-pressure blower to increase recirculated

Fig. 4.29. An EGR system arrangement [31]

gas pressure before reintroduction to the engine scavenge air and automated valves for isolation of the system [3, 33]. The EGR installation and its parameters are presented in Figs. 4.29-4.31.

Fig. 4.30. NO_x emission efficiency in relation to engine load and EGR level

Fig. 4.31. Effect of EGR exhaust gas temperature on the NO_x reduction ratio

Fig. 4.32. Changes in engine efficiency and SFOC under the influence of EGR

Fig. 4.33. NO_x emission at different engine loads as a function of oxygen content in the scavenge air [21]

The natural result of using EGR is the negative effect on the engine efficiency, which decreases with the increasing EGR ratio almost linearly, as shown in Fig. 4.32.

The investigation on the two-stroke marine diesel engine (4T50ME-X) has shown that IMO Tier III NO_x compliance is achievable by the use of high-pressure EGR solely. A cycle value below 3.4 g/kWh of NO_x was obtained, and also the not-to-exceed (NTE) level of 5.1 g/kWh of NO_x at each engine load point 25, 50, 75 and 100% was proven during the test. The results are shown in Fig. 4.33.

Conclusion: EGR can be used to meet the strict standard of IMO and it can assist other technologies. However, the high level of recirculation may result in increased CO and particulate emissions, which may be controlled using additional techniques such as water in fuel to achieve an optimum balance between NO_x, CO and PM. Due to the nature of EGR systems' primary engine controls, system malfunction or deviations from the normal operation can significantly reduce engine efficiency and increase CO and PM. There is also a risk of greatly accelerated engine wear and increased maintenance requirements if the scrubber does not clean and cool the exhaust gas to the required levels.

Non-thermal plasma: Non-thermal plasma has been introduced as a promising method for NO_x as well as PM removal. This system represents gas, which has been ionized into a mixture of highly reactive molecules. Plasma is created by means of high-voltage discharges. It is generated using an alternating high voltage to break-down the gas flowing between two electrodes. The region between two electrodes is filled with a material resulting in voltage breakdowns in the voids between the materials. The duration of the voltage breakdowns lies in the range of few nanoseconds. The system is compact and very flexible in terms of size and shape. The generated electric field produces free electrons, which travel through the gas creating O• and OH• radicals and they are effective in oxidizing exhaust gas emission compounds and therefore in reducing of harmful components.

In general, NTP can be generated in several ways, such as through electrical corona discharges, radio-frequency discharges, microwave discharges, dielectric barrier discharges and electron beams. To date, in connection with marine diesel engines exhausts, the dielectric barrier discharger (DBD) was commonly used [34-36].

As mentioned before, the NO_x in engine exhausts is composed primarily of NO. Consequently, after-treatment schemes have focused on the reduction of NO. NTP is able to convert NO to NO₂ by the oxygen radicals. It is also possible in the presence of water, oxygen and hydrocarbon, while only partially oxidizing the hydrocarbons. The non-thermal plasma module for marine use requires robust design, low voltage, minimum maintenance, and low energy consumption with easily scalable efficiency, as the rate of NO_x emission varies with engine load and external ship conditions.

An example of plasma operation process on engine exhaust gas is presented in Fig. 4.34. It can be observed that when the power supply of plasma reactor is turned off, the NO and NO₂ outlet concentration in the gas passing through the reactor correlates to the total NO_x level recorded at the reactor inlet. When plasma reactor is under operation, NO oxidation to NO₂ proves to be quite stable and efficient [34].

Combination of NTP reactor and other post-treatment methods can also be implemented. Novel techniques for cleaning the exhaust gases is non-thermal plasma are currently investigated: NTP reactor in presence of catalyst plasma-based catalytic treatment (PBCT) or NO_x reduction by non-thermal plasma and temperature swing adsorption (TSA). NTP assembly can be also combined with a diesel particulate filter (DPF). Hybrid methods are presented in Figs. 4.35-4.37. Conclusion: NTP do not generate any additional wastes (wastewater) and it is also not consisted of many different parts (no additional tanks, storage installations). If necessary, this technology may not use the catalyst, urea or other reducing agent and the operating temperature can be lower than 150°C. Main disadvantages of NTP technology are high energy consumption and expensive price [38] and it will have a low treatment efficiency in the condition of excess O₂. While generating NTP through the electrical corona discharge, the electron energy is below 10 eV, which results in an increase in gas temperature. While using the electron beam technology, accelerators cause ionization of the gas and thereafter formation of free radicals. Therefore,

Fig. 4.34. An example of NTP reactor operation [34]

Fig. 4.35. Installation for NO_x plasma-based catalytic treatment [37]

Fig. 4.36. Marine diesel engine exhaust using NTP treatment process – adsorption [31]

Fig. 4.37. Marine diesel engine exhaust using NTP treatment process – desorption [31]

in the corona discharge for one NO atom (oxidation) about 50 eV is required whereas for electron beam technology it is 18 eV.

4.3. Cost analysis

As the high efficient SO_x removal techniques are well known for many years, the main problem is an initial and running cost of an appropriate NO_x removal method. As shown in Table 4.15, there are many technologies for NO_x reduction. Tier II is responded by internal engine tuning including fuel injection timing retard, the arrangement of fuel valve injecting holes, and the optimization of the scavenging and exhaust systems. However, internal engine tuning cannot meet the requirements of Tier III, where a significant NO_x reduction is required. There are two main types of measures for Tier III.

Table 4.15. The cost of different NO_x reduction techniques [39]

Item	NO _x reduction rate (vs. Tier I)	Decrease of fuel efficiency	Technology	Initial cost	Running cost
Engine specification optimization (mechanical type engine)	Δ20%	+2~+3%	existing	small	small
Electronic control engine	Δ20%	0~+1%	developed	middle	small
Water injection	water emulsified fuel: Δ50%	+2~+3%	developed	middle	middle
	independent water injection: Δ80%	+7~+10%	developed	middle	middle
	stratified fuel water injection: Δ80% (For restriction of fuel pump capacity etc., actual reduction rate will be at the Δ40% level)	approx. +10%	developed	middle	middle
EGR with scrubber	Δ80%	+1~+3%	developed (basic tests complete)	large	middle
SCR	Δ80%~90%	0~+1%	developed (onboard test carried out)	large	large

To date, the only proven technique, which is surely able to meet the strict IMO Tier III limits is the combination of SCR + low sulphur marine diesel oil (MDO) or SCR + seawater for wet scrubbing system (SWS).

For an exemplary single trip, emission quantity ($m_{e,trip}$) can be calculated for standby (sb), manoeuvring (m) and cruise (c) modes of the ship as follows [40]:

$$m_{e,trip} = m_{e,sb} + m_{e,m} + m_{e,c}$$

Two different methods can be used to estimate ship emissions. They are based either on fuel consumption or engine power. When fuel consumption for each phase of the trip is known, $m_{e,trip}$ can be computed by:

$$m_{e,trip} = \sum_{Ph} (m_{f,i,j} \cdot EF_{i,j} \cdot ER)$$

where: m_f is the fuel consumption, EF is the fuel emission factor in kg/kg_f, i is the pollutant type, j is the fuel type and Ph is the phase of the trip. It includes cruise, manoeuvring, and standby with engine load of 80, 20, and 5%, respectively. ER is emissions reduction percentage in case of using emission control method.

When running time (T), power (P), load (L), and emission factor (E) in kg/kWh of an engine for a specific trip is known, $m_{e,trip}$ can be calculated using another equation:

$$m_{e,trip} = \sum_{Ph} (T \cdot P_{i,j} \cdot L_{i,j} \cdot E_{i,j} \cdot ER)$$

Diesel engine emission factors at low loads increase as the load decreases because of the increased specific fuel consumption and consequently the reduced efficiency. The exemplary values of medium-speed diesel engine emission factors (with MDO 1.0% of S, the speed of the main engine – 750 rpm) can be shown in Table 4.16.

Table 4.16. Medium-speed diesel engine emission factors [40]

Fuel type	Emission factor [g/kWh]	NO _x	SO _x	PM	CO ₂	CO	HC
MDO (1.0% S)	at cruise	13.2	3.97	0.47	646.08	1.1	0.5
	at manoeuvring	11.85	6.079	0.3211	869.1	4.344	1.132

Emission factors are increased in manoeuvring modes as engine load decreases. This trend results because at low loads specific fuel consumption of diesel engines is increased with reduced engine power and efficiency. Thus, mass emissions (in g/h) will be decreased at low loads while emission factor (in g/kW) will be increased.

Economic analysis for emission control methods: The annualized capital cost recovery (ACC) due to applying emission control method (ECM) depends on the capital cost value (CC), the average expected ship age after conversion (n), and the interest rate (r). ACC can be calculated as:

$$ACC = CC \cdot \frac{r(1+r)^n}{r(1+r)^n - 1}$$

Economically, applying either SCR or SWS systems will add extra annual installation costs (AIS) for the ship. These costs include ACC, annual maintenance and running costs (MC), fuel cost increment (Δ MGO) in case of using marine gas oil instead of SWS for SO_x reduction. AIS can be calculated as:

$$AIS = \sum_{ECM} ACC + \sum_{ECM} MC + \Delta MGO$$

Finally, annual cost-effectiveness for each ECM (ACE_{ECM}) can be calculated separately for each pollutant. This involves calculating ACC, annual operating and maintenance costs (MC) and annual emission reduction (AR) in tons/year. ACE_{ECM} can be calculated as:

$$ACE = \frac{ACC + MC}{AR}$$

The aim of SCR and SWS is to reduce exhaust gases emissions especially SO_x, NO_x and PM emissions. SCR reduces NO_x emissions by 90%, which would comply with required IMO emission levels. It depends on injecting urea solution into the exhaust gas stream in combination with catalyst housing in the exhaust channel. Compact SCR system consists of a reactor, which contains several catalyst layers, a treating and storage system for the reagent, and a control

system. It has an average volume of 1.0 m³/MW and a weight of 1.0 kg/kW, including urea storage tanks, pumps, injection and control system. Urea consumption rate for SCR system is 0.025 m³/MWh onboard ships. On the other hand, both SWS and MGO reduce SO_x emissions. The use of SWS system will reduce SO_x and PM emissions by 98% and 70%, respectively, while the use of MGO (0.1% sulphur) will reduce sulphur emission rates from 3.97 g/kWh to 0.4 g/kWh with a reduction of 90%. In addition, PM emissions will be changed from 0.47 g/kWh to 0.19 g/kWh with a reduction of 60%. Nitrogen oxides and CO₂ emissions are unchanged. In order to reduce both NO_x and SO_x emissions, a combined system of SCR, SWS and MGO can be used as shown in Fig. 4.38. MGO is mainly used to reduce SO_x emissions.

Fig. 4.38. Ship emission reduction with various strategies [40]

The yearly diesel engine NO_x, SO_x, CO₂, and PM emissions are 223.8, 68.31, 11.086 and 7.926 tons/year, respectively. A combined system of SCR and MGO leads to a reduction of NO_x, SO_x and PM emissions with percentages of 90, 90 and 60%, respectively. These emissions can be reduced using SCR and SWS systems by 90, 98, and 70%, respectively. Dual-fuel engine with 5% diesel oil and 95% natural gas can be compared with other ECMs. The highest CO₂ emission reduction is achieved by dual-fuel engines. This is due to lower carbon content in natural gas compared with diesel oil. Economically, the ECM can be judged from average installation cost per kW of engine power, annual cost for capital cost recovery and annual cost-effectiveness for ECM. For this study, fuel costs were examined in terms of their cost efficiency. According to local prices, MGO cost is 193.5 \$/m³ at the end of the year 2016. The capital cost of installing SWS onboard ship is 160 \$/kW with operating costs about 3% from this [40]. In addition, initial SCR investment cost rate is 50,000 \$/MW with 3.75 \$/MWh and 0.9 \$/MWh for running and maintenance costs, respectively. According to the literature, the main SCR component, the catalyst, requires rebuilding depending on the sulphur content (in %) by weight in fuel during operation. The reactor requires rebuilding in 15-20 years for S < 0.2 and in 5 years for 0.2 < S ≤ 1.5. For the case study, catalyst reactor has to be rebuilt every five years when used in SCR + SWS system where MDO contains 1.0% of sulphur. It needs rebuilding after 15 years when MGO with 0.1% of sulphur content is used. Figure 4.39 shows the annual and average installation costs for ECMs.

The installation costs for SCR and SWS are 175,895 \$/year and 244,358 \$/year, respectively with average engine output power cost of 20.35 \$/kW and 28.28 \$/kW, respectively. In addition, applying combined SCR + SWS and SCR + MGO will increase the ship annual operating costs by 420,252 \$/year and 384,453 \$/year, respectively, with average installation costs of 48.6 \$/kW and 44.5 \$/kW, respectively. In addition, the total installation and maintenance costs for the dual-fuel engine is 258,030 \$/year with 29.9 \$/kW average cost per output power. Annualized cost-effectiveness of each ERM can be used for choosing the suitable method for

Fig. 4.39. Average and annual costs for applying different ECMs [40]

Fig. 4.40. Annual cost-effectiveness for NO_x and SO_x emission reduction measures [40]

Fig. 4.41. Annual cost-effectiveness [40]

emission reduction. It compares the total annual capital and maintenance costs with the amount of emission reduction after applying exhaust reduction method. Figure 4.40 shows the cost-effectiveness for the reduction of NO_x and SO_x emissions using SCR, SWS and MGO.

The cost-effectiveness for reducing NO_x emissions using SCR is 873.5 \$/ton for the reduced 201.4 tons annually. SO_x emissions can be reduced by 61.48 tons/year and 66.94 tons/year with the cost-effectiveness of 3392 \$/ton and 3115 \$/ton using MGO and SWS, respectively. In addition, combined systems of SCR, SWS and MGO can be used to reduce exhaust gas emissions in order to comply with new IMO regulations. Figure 4.41 shows the proposed two combined system compared with dual-fuel engines.

Using SCR + MGO system would reduce NO_x and SO_x for the case study with the cost-effectiveness of 1909 \$/ton and 6254 \$/ton, respectively. The reduction of these emissions can be achieved using (SCR + SWS) with the cost-effectiveness of 6836 \$/ton and 6278 \$/ton, respectively. The more economical option for reducing NO_x, SO_x and CO₂ emissions is using the dual-fuel engine with the cost-effectiveness of 1486, 4084 and 160.8 \$/ton, respectively.

4.4. Simultaneous removal of NO_x and SO_x

Currently, many ship emission control techniques have been developed. However, most of these technically available technologies are applied to remove NO_x or SO₂ separately. Few studies have been reported concentrating on the simultaneous removal of NO_x and SO₂ in one process, but to date, there is no established technology opted for simultaneous removal of multi-gas pollutants for ocean-going vessels.

There was a proposition of an integrated system, which consisted of a monolithic Pt/Al₂O₃ oxidation catalyst and a seawater scrubber [41]. It managed to achieve a single compact device for simultaneous abatement of multi-gas pollutants. However, due to the limited sulphur resistance of the catalyst, this system could only be used with fuel sulphur content of up to 0.4%.

Another research project developed a hybrid process of electron beam irradiation plus seawater scrubbing to clean flue gas from marine diesel engines [42]. The active species formed in the plasma reaction converted NO into NO₂, which favoured seawater absorption. From the viewpoint of industrial application, this kind of integrated process for multi-gas pollutants removal may be especially suitable for ocean-going ships. It shows a great potential to reduce the equipment footprint and complexity of the system. Nonetheless, high SO₂ removal up to 99% and NO_x up to 51% were obtained for exhaust gases with 1700 ppmv of NO_x concentration even if high irradiation doses were applied. As the NO_x removal is far below the 80-90%, this method cannot compliance with IMO Tier III regulations.

NO_x removal by wet scrubbing methods has not been adopted on ships because of the low solubility of NO (accounting for more than 90% of NO_x) [39]. However, many wet scrubbing systems for SO_x removal using seawater have been successfully used on ships. In addition, various chemical oxidants have been introduced in wet scrubbing technology for NO_x removal [43]. In general, oxidizing agents, such as sodium chlorite, potassium permanganate, chlorine dioxide or hydrogen peroxide, are added to the scrubbing medium to convert insoluble NO to soluble NO₂ [44-49]. These oxidants achieved satisfying removal efficiencies in lab-scale and pilot-scale experiments. There have been many reports on the enhancement of wet scrubbers' performances. For NO_x gases removing, HNO₃ and Ag(I) mixture in an integrated wet scrubber electrochemical system was investigated [50]. NO_x was removed from the gas stream with 75% efficiency when the liquid/gas flow rate was 400 L/m³. Another study has shown, that it is possible to use a sieve tray wet scrubber for removing NO gas. NaClO₂ was used as the scrubber medium to convert insoluble NO to soluble NO₂, which could then be removed by alkaline solution. This system could remove NO_x from the flue gas stream with 51.5% efficiency using a liquid/gas flow rate of 7 L/m³ [46]. In another case, aqueous chlorine dioxide was used as the scrubbing solution in a bubbling reactor to remove NO_x from flue gas. Using a liquid/gas flow rate of 44 L/m³, it was possible to remove NO_x with 60% efficiency [51]. Because wet scrubbers use mostly high liquid/gas flow rates, it is very common to have water pollution problems. High

concentrations of absorbents are also used to improve removal efficiency in wet scrubbers, which not only causes environmental problems but also leads to significant corrosion problems inside and outside the nozzles, tubes, and walls of scrubbers. There was a work, where 100% SO₂ removal, 100% NO oxidation, and 81% NO_x removal efficiency were attained in a novel swirl scrubber using NaClO₂ as the scrubber medium [43]. The NO_x removal efficiency increased mainly with decreasing solution pH value. Increasing the initial SO₂ concentration enhanced the NO_x removal efficiency, and this enhancement was more intense at higher pH values. A higher removal efficiency was obtained with increasing sodium chlorite concentration, but a supply of sodium chlorite above 0.2 M did not improve the removal efficiency considerably. The swirl scrubber of this study produced very large gas-liquid interfacial areas, and therefore, high removal efficiencies were observed using a low concentration of scrubbing medium and a low L/G ratio. Another promising NO_x and SO₂ removal method for ship emissions based on seawater electrolysis technology was proposed and investigated in the semi-batch process [10]. Results of NO_x removal by electrolysed seawater showed that NO_x removal efficiencies increased with increasing active chlorine concentration of electrolysed seawater and O₂ concentration, but decreased with increasing gas flow rate. Relatively high removal efficiencies of NO and NO_x were possible to reach when the initial pH was in a range of 4-6. NO_x removal efficiencies were less sensitive to the change of NO inlet concentration, CO₂ concentration, and reaction temperature. For simultaneous removal of NO_x and SO₂ from simulated ship emissions (NO_x – 1000 ppm, O₂ – 15% CO₂ – 5%, SO₂ – 0-751 ppm), NO_x removal efficiencies in single stage and double stage experiments were more than 60% and 90%, respectively, under conditions of gas flow rate 1.26 L/min, absorbent volume 750 mL per stage, active chlorine concentration 1500 mg/L Cl₂, pH 7, and reaction temperature 20°C.

5. ELECTRON BEAM

5.1. Introduction

To date, only several studies concentrating on the simultaneous removal of NO_x and SO₂ in one process (using electrolysis or electromagnetic techniques) have been carried out [3, 10, 46, 49]. To accomplish major reductions in SO_x and NO_x emissions, a new onboard installation of exhaust emission control is required and it may be an EBFGT process, which is one of the most effective methods of removing SO₂ and NO_x from industrial flue gases.

Electron accelerators are reliable and durable electrically sourced equipment that can produce ionizing radiation when it is needed for a particular commercial use. There are a large number of electron accelerators being used worldwide in industrial applications, most of which involve polymer processing. Nowadays, there are over 1700 electron beam units, providing an estimated added value to numerous products, amounting to 100 billion \$ or more [52]. High-current electron accelerators are used in diverse industries to enhance the physical and chemical properties of materials and to reduce undesirable contaminants such as pathogens, toxic by-products, or emissions. Over the past few decades, electron beam technologies have been developed aimed at ensuring the safety of gaseous and liquid effluents discharged to the environment. It has been demonstrated that electron beam technologies for flue gas treatment (SO_x and NO_x removal), wastewater purification, and sludge hygienization can be effectively deployed to mitigate environmental degradation. Recently, extensive work has been carried out on the use of electron beam for environmental remediation, which also includes the removal of emerging contaminants such as VOCs, endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs), and potential EDCs [53].

EBFGT is still a relatively new approach that was presented for the first time in Japan in the 1970s for the removal of SO₂ from exhaust gases [54]. However, this technology has been already successfully implemented on an industrial scale at coal-fired power plants in China

(Chengdu and Hangzhou) [42] as well as in Poland (Szczecin ‘Pomorzany’). The main parameters of these three industrial electron beam plants are presented in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1. Main parameters of three industrial electron beam plants [42]

Parameters	Unit	Chengdu TPP China	Hangzhou TPP China	Pomorzany EPS Poland
Nominal flue gas flow rate	Nm ³ /h	300 000	305 400	270 000
Inlet gas temperature	°C	150	145	140
Inlet SO ₂ concentration	ppmv	1 800	970	700
Inlet NO _x concentration	ppmv	400	200	295
SO ₂ removal efficiency	%	80	85	95
NO _x removal efficiency	%	18	55	70
Electron beam parameters	keV mA	800 2 x 400	800 2 x 400	700 4 x 375

The process applied onboard is quite a different system from reported above. All of these installations were dry ammonia processes, using ammonia as the reagent. The system consisted of the following equipment in line: dry ESP (fly ash removal), humidification tower, accelerator driven process vessel, product collector – dry ESP, product granulation and packing installation as well as the ammonia storage and injection system. This type of technology, unit operation and process equipment are not feasible for maritime applications. Moreover, while thinking about this technology in relation to the newest strict IMO Tier III regulation, the efficiency of NO_x removal is insufficient (removal of 80% of NO_x outside the ECA and removal of 90% of NO_x inside the ECA are required). The other type of accelerators (low energy self-shielded units < 300 keV) have to be applied. For comparison, in the case of classical TV tube energy of the beam is equal to ca. 20 keV. Having considered that matter, the Institute of Nuclear Chemistry and Technology (Poland) undertook the study about complete, reliable and compact technology for gaseous pollutants removal that would meet Tier III standards and would be a real alternative for currently available onboard hazardous gas removal systems.

5.2. Process key parameters

In the electron beam technology, electrons are accelerated by a high voltage in a vacuum region before being injected through thin foil windows to the flue gases at the atmospheric-pressure processing chamber (plasma reactor). The energetic electrons collide with exhaust gas molecules and produce reactive free radicals, atoms, ions and secondary electrons that decompose the pollutants molecules in the irradiated flue gases. During this process, pollutants such as SO₂ and NO_x are oxidized to higher oxides which then react with the water vapour present in the flue gases, resulting in the formation of H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ [54].

Fig. 5.1. The general scheme of the electron beam interaction with the flue gas

The general scheme of the electron beam interaction with the flue gas is given in Fig. 5.1.

There are different key parameters, which have a significant influence on process effectiveness [42, 52-54]:

- inlet NO_x and SO_2 concentrations,
- irradiation dose,
- SO_2/NO_x inlet concentration ratio,
- temperature.

To date, in order to investigate such parameters influence on electron beam exhaust gas treatment system, a number of tests have been carried out. The studies of this process can be divided into three parts:

- irradiation by electron beam (NO_x and SO_2 removal),
- irradiation by electron beam + wet scrubber (NO_x and SO_2 removal),
- irradiation by electron beam + wet scrubber + NaClO_2 (NO_x removal).

Irradiation by electron beam: The influence of the inlet NO concentration on the efficiency of NO_x removal was firstly examined (no reagents, no scrubbing). Results indicated that increasing the NO inlet concentration from 200 ppm to 1000 ppm in such a case caused a significant decrease in the removal efficiency of NO_x . It can be explained that with the inlet NO concentration increase, more oxidant species, e.g. OH and O_3 , are used to oxidize NO into NO_2 which is still present in the gas phase. To increase NO_x removal efficiency, more oxidant species are needed, e.g. OH , to oxidize NO_2 into HNO_3 which can be removed from the gas phase. However the water concentration in the gas mixture is constant in the experimental conditions and $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals generated from water radiolysis mainly depends on the absorbed dose, the ratio between concentration of $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals to total concentration of NO and NO_2 decreases with increasing inlet concentration of NO , thus the NO_x ($\text{NO} + \text{NO}_2$) removal efficiency decreases significantly during the concentration range of 200 ppm to 1000 ppm. This led to the conclusion that when exhaust gases contain high concentrations of NO , increasing the dose is not a sufficient or cost-effective method and an alternative solution has to be considered. SO_2 influence on NO_x removal efficiency was studied for the high and low inlet concentration of NO . In the low inlet concentration of NO (200 ppm), a relatively high removal efficiency of NO was obtained. By increasing the SO_2 inlet concentration, the removal efficiency of NO increased noticeably, especially at a higher irradiation dose.

The effect of the presence of SO_2 in enhancing NO_x removal efficiency can be explained by the chain of reactions (5.5, 5.6, 5.4, 5.7). Radicals $\text{HO}_2\bullet$, which are produced during reactions with SO_2 (reactions (5.5) and (5.6)), react with NO and oxidize them into NO_2 (reaction (5.4)). This is later converted to HNO_3 (reaction (5.7)). When the NO inlet concentration is high, this synergistic effect is more advantageous at high concentrations of SO_2 . When the NO_x inlet concentration was low or high, an increase in temperature increased the NO_x removal efficiency. The temperature did not have a significant impact on NO_x removal efficiency at a high NO inlet

concentration (1000 ppm). Similarly to NO, when the SO₂ inlet concentration increases, the efficiency of its removal decreases. This effect is less significant compared to that of NO.

In contrast to the analogous dependence study on NO_x removal efficiency, a higher NO inlet concentration resulted in lower SO₂ removal efficiency. The explanation of this phenomenon is based on competing reactions. SO₂, as well as NO₂, uses •OH radicals during the oxidation to the higher oxides. However, the reaction between NO₂ and •OH (reaction (5.7)) has a higher rate constant than the reaction between SO₂ and •OH (reaction (5.5)), which results in the predominance of NO_x removal over that of SO₂.

Temperature influence on SO₂ removal efficiency was also studied. The removal efficiency of SO₂, in contrast to that of NO_x, was higher when the temperature was lower. 90°C was chosen as an optimal temperature at which reasonably high removal efficiencies of SO₂ and NO_x were obtained.

Irradiation by electron beam + wet SO_x scrubber: In the second part of the experiments electron beam technology was coupled with the wet scrubbing method. The purpose of the hybrid technology was to enhance the removal efficiency of NO_x and SO₂, especially when the inlet concentration of pollutants in exhaust gases is high. In the experiment, outlet gas was bubbled through simulated seawater filled glass probe. This arrangement corresponds to the single scrubber plate (in a high ship scrubber there are a number of plates). Comparisons of NO_x removal efficiency were made under two experimental conditions: the sole use of the electron beam, and the use of wet scrubber after electron beam.

In both cases, the removal efficiency of NO_x increased significantly when the hybrid technology was used. The relatively high removal efficiency of NO_x was obtained at a lower absorbed dose, thus reducing energy consumption for NO_x removal, especially for high inlet concentrations of NO. NO_x consists mainly of NO and NO₂. Under electron beam irradiation, NO is first oxidized to NO₂. When seawater was used as a wet scrubbing solution, NO₂ was removed from the gas stream due to its high solubility in seawater; thus NO_x removal efficiency increased.

When hybrid technology was used, the tendency was the same as when the sole electron beam was applied; higher NO inlet concentration resulted in lower NO_x removal efficiency. However, the effect was not as significant as when electron beam technology only was used. The influence of SO₂ inlet concentration on NO_x removal efficiency was also studied in the hybrid process of electron beam coupled with a wet scrubber. An increase of SO₂ inlet concentration resulted in an increase in NO_x removal efficiency, a similar phenomenon was observed for the electron beam process. However, the effect in the hybrid process was less significant than that in the electron beam process. The SO₂ removal efficiency was also examined after hybrid technology treatment and compared with the results achieved with electron beam technology. Experiments showed that removal efficiency of SO₂ was much higher when hybrid technology was applied. Efficiencies as high as 93% were obtained for high doses (21.8 kGy and 32.7 kGy). When lower doses were applied the removal efficiency was near or above 80%.

Irradiation by electron beam + wet scrubber + NaClO₂: The main problem during the third part of the study was to accomplish the NO_x removal efficiency, which should meet IMO Tier III standards inside the ECA. The block diagram of EB + SWS + NaClO₂ process is presented in Fig. 5.2.

During the third part of the study, 25 mM of NaClO₂ and the appropriate amount of Michaelis buffer, maintaining the water pH at 6.25 were added to the seawater. The gas flow was around 5 m³/h and inlet concentrations of NO_x and SO₂ were equal to 1000 ppmv and 700 ppmv, respectively. The inlet temperature of the gases varies between 350°C and 400°C.

The irradiated waste gases are introduced from the bottom of the column and flow countercurrently to the sprayed process water. There is a direct gas-liquid interaction. NaClO₂ oxidizes the remaining after the irradiation NO and thereafter, at the appropriate pH 6-7 of the solution, it absorbs NO₂ with simultaneous production of nitric and hydrochloric acids. Both acids are neutralized by components of high alkalinity of process water. The post-reaction water flows down the column, where it is discharged to the purification set.

Fig. 5.2. E + SWS + NaClO₂ block diagram: 1 – inlet to the installation, 2 – inlet gas parameters, 3 – heat exchanger (outlet temperature 70-90°C), 4 – process chamber, 5 – accelerator, 6 – accelerator's shelter, 7 – wet simple spray tower scrubber, 8 – demister, 9 – outlet gas parameters (of scrubber), 10 – process water (fresh), 11 – NaClO₂, 12 – Michaelis buffer Na₂HPO₄ and KH₂PO₄, 13 – seawater, 14 – NaCl solution, 15 – fresh water, 16 – centrifugal separator, 17 – sludge tank, 18 – post-reaction water tank, 19 – monitoring system of post-reaction water, 20 – sewage or sea, 21 – exhaust fan, 22 – stack, 23 – re-circulation (optional)

Fig. 5.3. E + SWS + NaClO₂ flowchart: 1 – inlet to the installation, 2 – inlet gas parameters, 3 – heat exchanger (outlet temperature 70-90°C), 4 – process chamber, 5 – accelerator, 6 – accelerator's shelter, 7 – wet barbotage tower scrubber, 8 – demister, 9 – outlet gas parameters (of scrubber), 10 – process water (fresh), 11 – NaClO₂, 12 – Michaelis buffer Na₂HPO₄ and KH₂PO₄, 13 – seawater, 14 – NaCl solution, 15 – fresh water, 16 – centrifugal separator, 17 – sludge tank, 18 – post-reaction water tank, 19 – monitoring system of post-reaction water, 20 – sewage or sea, 21 – exhaust fan, 22 – stack, 23 – re-circulation (optional)

As explained in detail in section 4.1, the efficiency of NO_x removal in the wet scrubber depends on the efficiency of gas-liquid interactions. The study has shown that significantly higher effectiveness of gas purification can be achieved while using a wet barbotage tower scrubber, where the interfacial area is considerably greater. However, the basic obstacles in using it are due to the dustiness of the exhaust gases and the permissible pressure drop in the scrubber. With high dustiness of the waste gases, exhaust gases may be clogged by a sieve flow gas distribution system at the inlet to the bubble scrubber. To avoid this, flue gases need to be dedusted. The block diagram of EB + SWS + NaClO_2 process with wet barbotage tower scrubber is presented in Fig. 5.3.

The obtained NO_x removal efficiency in comparison to the previous study is shown in Fig. 5.4. In this version of tests, NO_x removal is above 90% and thus meeting Tier III requirements was obtained.

Fig. 5.4. The comparison of the NO_x removal efficiency between technology using electron beam only, hybrid technology, where electron beam was coupled with wet scrubber, and hybrid technology, where electron beam was coupled with wet scrubber as well as with NaClO_2 and buffer (the inlet SO_2 concentration was 700 ppm and NO was 1000 ppm). EB – irradiation of gases with the electron beam from the accelerator, SWS – seawater scrubber, buffer – Michaelis buffer

The removal efficiency of SO_2 , in a similar way as in classic scrubbers depends on the scrubber height (number of theoretical absorption plates), liquid/gas ratio and solution alkalinity. Therefore, if over 50% can be achieved in a single step which corresponds roughly to one theoretic plate, it is possible to reduce the height of the absorber.

5.3. Accelerators for onboard applications

As it was stated before, the accelerators to be applied on the ship are different type units in comparison with those applied in power industry for coal-fired boiler flue gas treatment. An example of the accelerator which may be applied to the discussed technology is presented in Fig. 5.5 and main parameters are given in Table 5.2.

If the shorter length is needed, the multicathode system has to be applied (Fig. 5.6). The size of the units in comparison with the operator is presented in Fig. 5.7.

Fig. 5.5. Electron accelerator with the linear cathode

Table 5.2. Main parameters of the accelerator

Parameter	Value
Accelerator voltage	75-250 kV
Electron beam current	0-2000 mA
Working length	400-3000 mm
Throughput	14 000 kGy m/min
Distribution of dosage over the working length	< +/- 10%
No cooling of the electron exit window necessary (at room temperature)	

Fig. 5.6. Accelerator with multiple linear cathodes

Fig. 5.7. Accelerator with the linear cathode and its operator

Fig. 5.8. Conceptual scheme of the installation using electron beam technology for SO_x and NO_x removal as applied onboard, water closed or hybrid system

Table 5.3. Steps for a new deSO_x and deNO_x installations onboard applications [55]

Initial phase	R&D works: process chemistry, process optimization, unit operations, equipment selection
Feasibility/concept engineering	Ship requirements, equipment configuration, concept/GA interfacing verifications, feasibility report, capex/opex estimates, project outline
Basic engineering, projects planning, contractors' selection	Basic engineering, preliminary approvals, final project plan, sub-contractors, selection, firm offer and contract for turnkey delivery
Detailed engineering and procurement	Completion of basic engineering, detailed engineering, procurement, drawings approvals from class, installation preparations
Construction and installation	Equipment delivery for prefabrication/installation, prefabrication, installation works and site management
Approvals and commissioning	Tests, approvals from flag/class, commissioning, crew training, hand over, start of lifecycle support

The scheme of planned system installation for simultaneous SO_x and NO_x removal is presented in Fig. 5.8.

The further R&D tests are being carried out for the process optimization, process engineering and will lead to the techno-economical assumptions elaboration. The closed or hybrid circulation system has to be developed during these experiments to ensure the standard composition of effluents to be discharged to the sea. The works will be performed in a laboratory leading to onshore test installation construction. The further implementation steps leading to pilot plant construction onboard are presented in Table 5.3.

5.4. Conclusions and recommendations

In order to protect human health and the environment, significant additional cuts in air pollutants emissions in accordance with IMO MARPOL Annex VI are necessary. Currently, several commercial technologies have been implemented onboard to reduce the level of SO_x and NO_x from marine diesel engines. Though these technologies can remove 99% of SO₂ and 90% of NO_x, they possess a number of important drawbacks. More often than not, two separate technologies for removal of NO_x and SO_x are necessary, which results in high installation cost. However, especially problematic is nitrogen monoxide (95% of all nitrogen oxides) due to its non-reactivity and insolubility. The most well-known NO_x removal system, SCR, is best suited for steady high-load conditions, i.e. SCR is less suited for low load operation and manoeuvring in coastal and harbour areas. The sensitivity of the chemistry between the cylinder and fuel oil also shows limitations for marine operation. This is further emphasized by the need to fit the SCR reactor before the turbocharger due to the required temperature regime. As already mentioned, above 90% of NO_x can be removed, however, some complications and limitations make it more difficult to apply SCR on marine vessels in service. This makes it unfeasible to remove more than 90-95% NO_x due to the risk of ammonia slip (ammonia passing through the SCR unreacted). If we compare the SCR installation on new ships to a retrofitted SCR system it becomes obvious that it is far more complicated to retrofit the installation than to integrate SCR as the ship is being built.

First of all, to find the required space for the catalyst, piping, support, auxiliary equipment, and NO_x, O₂, and NH₃ measuring devices is a challenge and the number of SCR systems installed on two-stroke diesel engines is still limited. Therefore, today an SCR system is specially designed for each main engine. Retrofitting is complicated and not recommendable if the vessel has not been prepared for later SCR installation. To avoid chemical compositions blocking the SCR, the sulphur content in the fuel oil used on engines with SCR is important as is, in particular, the lower exhaust gas temperature limit at the inlet engine. Furthermore, some SO_x will be converted to SO₃ in the SCR catalyst and thus create visible smoke. When installing the SCR catalyst, it is important to compensate the exhaust pipe and the component support for vibrations and temperature changes.

Taking everything into consideration, SCR is most common and well-known NO_x removal system on stationary outposts, but it is not the best solution for marine vessels, due to numbers of limits and disadvantages, such as high installation cost, significant dimensions or necessity of catalyst removal as well as inconvenient process conditions.

Different other solutions, like humid air motor, exhaust gas recirculation or some simultaneous SO₂ and NO_x removal systems have been also investigated in relation to the new MARPOL Annex VI limits, but, to date, they are insufficient or they were not tested enough to be successfully implemented onboard and to meet Tier III strict regulations. Hence, to accomplish major reductions in both SO_x and NO_x emissions, a new onboard installation of exhaust emission control is required and it may be an electron beam flue gas treatment process, which is one of the most effective methods of removing SO₂ and NO_x from industrial flue gases.

The study was performed in the laboratory plant with NO_x concentration up to 1700 ppmv and SO₂ concentration up to 1000 ppmv. Such high NO_x and SO₂ concentrations were observed in the exhaust gases from marine high-power diesel engines fuelled with different heavy fuel

oils. In the first part of the study, the simulated exhaust gases were irradiated by the electron beam from the accelerator. The simultaneous removal of SO₂ and NO_x were obtained and their removal efficiencies strongly depend on irradiation dose and inlet NO_x concentration. For NO_x concentrations above 800 ppmv, low removal efficiencies were obtained even if applied high doses. In the second part of the study, the irradiated gases were directed to the seawater scrubber for further purification. The scrubbing process enhances removal efficiencies of both pollutants. The SO₂ removal efficiencies above 98.5% were obtained with irradiation dose greater than 5.3 kGy (in one theoretical plate scrubber only). For inlet NO_x concentrations of 1700 ppmv the NO_x removal efficiency about 51% was obtained with the dose greater than 8.8 kGy. In the third part of the study, 25 mM NaClO₂ and the appropriate amount of Michaelis buffer, maintaining the water pH at 6.25 were added to the seawater. The exhaust gas was first irradiated with the electron beam technology to reduce the NO, in the dose range of 10-12 kGy with a temperature of the exhaust gas not exceeding 90°C and then followed by a wet scrubber method with appropriately prepared process water, with an addition of the strong oxidant NaClO₂. Further research on closed loop applications is needed. In this version of tests, NO_x removal was above 90% and thus meeting Tier III requirements was obtained.

The results of this study indicate that electron beam combined with wet scrubbing and NaClO₂ oxidant is a very promising technology to be applied in the simultaneous reduction of high concentrations of NO_x and SO₂ emitted from diesel engines on ships, which are the main sources of SO₂ and NO_x pollution along their navigation routes. No solid state catalyst is required and reactor cross-section is free of any packing. It is now required, to execute the full material and energy balance as well as the equipment cost analysis and thereafter realization of the first test onboard. These data will be obtained when planned R&D programme will be concluded. The steps to be carried out before pilot plant onboard installation was presented at the end of the paper.

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6. LITERATURE

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